

CIRCULAR ECONOMY

CiNURGi

Nutrient recycling in the Baltic Sea Region

State-of-the-art and the way forward

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Institute of Soil Science
and Plant Cultivation
State Research Institute

CLIMATE-NEUTRAL SOCIETIES

This #MadeWithInterreg project helps drive the transition to a green and resilient Baltic Sea region and is part of the EU-funded Interreg Baltic Sea Region (BSR) core project #C049, titled CiNURGi, under the 2021-2027 PROGRAMME, Priority 3: Climate-Neutral Societies, Objective 3.1: Circular Economy.

**Organisations from the following countries cooperate together to make that happen:
Sweden (LP), Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Lithuania and Poland.**

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State-of-the-art and the way forward

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Foreword

CiNURGi (Circular Nutrients for a Sustainable Baltic Sea Region) is an Interreg Baltic Sea Region Core Project accelerating the circular economy for nutrients across the region. By strengthening infrastructure, technology, and policy, the project advances recovery and safe return of nutrients from agricultural, municipal, and industrial streams. CiNURGi is aligned with the HELCOM Baltic Sea Regional Nutrient Recycling Strategy, the EU Circular Economy Action Plan under the European Green Deal, and the Farm to Fork Strategy's Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan. The project runs from November 2023 to October 2026.

This report corresponds to Work Package 1, Activity 1, which maps nutrient-rich biomasses and their current treatment in the Baltic Sea Region. It establishes a comparable baseline for the status of nutrient recycling in the region's EU Member States, providing a clear starting point for targeted measures and enabling cross-border learning where countries are at different stages.

We acknowledge the contribution of our consortium, 24 partners and 13 associated organizations, from Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, and Sweden. Their commitment and expertise are essential to the project's progress.

For more information about CiNURGi and its activities, please visit our project homepage: <https://interreg-baltic.eu/project/cinurgi/>

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction.....	2
2 State-of-the-art in nutrient recycling in the BSR.....	3
2.1 Finland.....	3
2.1.1 Background.....	3
2.1.2 Current practices.....	4
2.1.3 Policy instruments to promote nutrient recycling.....	7
2.1.4 Challenges in nutrient recycling.....	8
2.2 Estonia.....	9
2.2.1 Background.....	9
2.2.2 Current practices.....	9
2.2.3 Policy instruments to promote nutrient recycling.....	11
2.3 Latvia.....	15
2.3.1 Current practices.....	15
2.3.2 Challenges in nutrient recycling.....	17
2.4 Lithuania.....	17
2.4.1 Background.....	17
2.4.2 Current practices.....	21
2.4.3 Policy instruments to promote nutrient recycling.....	24
2.4.4 Challenges in nutrient recycling.....	26
2.5 Poland.....	27
2.5.1 Background.....	27
2.5.2 Current status.....	27
2.5.3 Regulation related to nutrient recycling.....	30
2.5.4 Challenges in nutrient recycling.....	31
2.5.5 Summary.....	31
2.6 Germany.....	32
2.6.1 Policy instruments to promote nutrient recycling.....	32
2.6.2 Current status.....	33
2.7 Denmark.....	42
2.7.1 Background.....	42
2.7.2 Current practices.....	42
2.7.3 Nutrient policies.....	45
2.8 Sweden.....	47

2.8.1	Background.....	47
2.8.2	Current Status.....	49
2.8.3	Challenges in nutrient recycling	53
3	Draft national nutrient recycling strategy	63
3.1	Mapping nutrient recycling potential.....	64
3.2	Setting targets for nutrient recycling	64
3.3	Measures to promote nutrient recycling	65
3.4	Monitoring the progress	66
3.5	Implementation and responsibilities	66
3.6	Financing	67
3.7	Alignment with EU and regional policies.....	67
4	Conclusions.....	69

Executive Summary

This Work Package 1, Activity 1 report describes the status of nutrient recycling in the Baltic Sea Region (BSR). The country-specific state-of-the-art is described for Finland, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Germany, Denmark and Sweden. The report aims at making the starting point of nutrient recycling visible so that countries can learn from one another, target gaps systematically and promote nutrient recycling in the future.

Across the BSR, there is substantial potential to return nitrogen and phosphorus to agriculture from different agricultural, municipal and industrial nutrient-rich biomasses. Now, practices to handle these biomass flows are variable and often optimized for waste handling rather than nutrient recovery and reuse. Some countries are also still working on improving separate collection of for instance municipal biowaste.

Economic feasibility is often the limiting factor for improved nutrient recycling. Advanced processing requires high investment and often produces products that struggle to match the delivered cost and convenience of mineral fertilizers. Also, regulation and quality assurance give restraints especially to sewage sludge -based nutrients.

Most countries lack consistent, comparable monitoring of nutrient recycling. To track the progress of nutrient recycling and highlight the areas in need of support, the report recommends development of monitoring system for each BSR country with designated and sufficiently resourced organization responsible for the monitoring process making best possible use of the data on the origin and handling nutrient-rich biomasses.

To promote nutrient recycling nationally and regionally, a nutrient recycling strategy can be used as a guiding light. While the BSR has the HELCOM Regional Nutrient Recycling Strategy already, national strategies with more detailed targets are mainly lacking. Thus, a template for such a document is given to assist BSR countries in developing national strategy papers.

Keywords

Nutrient recycling; Circular economy; Baltic Sea Region; Phosphorus; Nitrogen; Processing; Policy instruments; Monitoring indicators.

1 Introduction

Sari Luostarinen, Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke)

Nutrients are needed the most in food and feed production as plant nutrients necessary for growth and high yields. The main nutrients required are nitrogen and phosphorus, while potassium and many micronutrients are also needed. In this report, the focus is on nitrogen and phosphorus.

Modern agriculture uses mostly mineral fertilizers. This means phosphorus mined from the mineral resources and nitrogen bound from the atmosphere to hydrogen to produce ammonia. Mineral phosphorus reserves are only available in certain regions of the world, many of them politically volatile, thus causing potential risks for phosphorus availability and price. Production of nitrogen fertilizers leans on an energy-intensive process using mainly natural gas and thus being located in countries with high natural gas resources. This has also proved a risk due to political volatility. Moreover, the environmental consequences of mineral fertilizer production and use are of concern.

Therefore, nutrient recycling has gained attention together as part of circular economy. The idea is to recover and reuse nutrients already being used in human activities. Ideally, this would be accomplished with reduced environmental impacts. In practice, nutrient recycling means identification of nutrients being present in agricultural, municipal and industrial activities and planning and implementing effective recovery methods to bring them back to use while minimizing losses into the environment.

The production and consumption activities in the different sectors of our societies result in different types of wastes and side streams. Some of these are rich in nutrients and therefore relevant for nutrient recycling. In agriculture, livestock manure and different plant biomasses can be recycled with reuse of the nutrient contained. Municipal source-sorted biowaste and sewage sludge from wastewater treatment are rich in nutrients and a potential source for nutrient recovery and reuse. Industrial processes can produce many kinds of nutrient-rich side streams, especially in the food processing industries.

Some of these recyclable biomasses can be reused directly, such as manure as a fertilizer, but most require processing to e.g. reduce volume, ensure hygiene and other quality requirements, and/or separate nutrients into different end-products. Many of the biomasses are already processed, but often not for the sake of efficient nutrient recycling, but to dispose of them in a way causing minimal harm. Still, nutrients are already being recycled, though often with rather inefficient ways. Therefore, to enhance nutrient recycling, the state-of-the-art needs to be known.

In this report, country-specific information on nutrient recycling was collected to identify its status in the Baltic Sea Region. The following chapters describe how different recyclable biomasses are currently being managed, how effective the recycling efforts are, and what can be identified as the main bottlenecks hindering the implementation of more efficient recycling activities. The report also includes a rough template for a regional nutrient recycling strategy to be used as starting point when working towards a more controlled promotion and implementation of nutrient recycling in each region/country.

2 State-of-the-art in nutrient recycling in the BSR

The Baltic Sea countries are in different stages of nutrient recycling. Even the concept of nutrient recycling may be differently understood with some being very active already for a long time and others just beginning to grasp on the idea of improving the nutrient cycles from the perspective of reuse, not only emission reduction. In this chapter, the state of the art of nutrient recycling in the EU countries of the Baltic Sea Region is described.

2.1 Finland

Sari Luostarinen, Elina Tampio & Johanna Laakso, Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke)

2.1.1 Background

Finland has been striving for being a model region for nutrient recycling since the declaration made in the Baltic Sea Action Summit in 2010. A memo of a working group led by then Prime Minister Matti Vanhanen (MMM 2011) lists the measures then identified to reach the target with the main ones titled as 1) Use nutrients with care and efficiency, 2) Minimize biowaste and the nutrients cycled in them, 3) Recycle nutrient effectively and safely, and 4) Recover nutrients from waterways and return them to use.

Since then and over several Government Programmes, nutrient recycling has been a constant topic supported by public funds. The Ministry of the Environment has offered project funding and investment support for progressing nutrient recycling especially in the fields of wastewater and waste management, while the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry has been offering support for nutrient recycling solutions in agriculture and use of recycled fertilizing products in a separate instrument and as part of CAP. The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment has also participated with investment support for large biogas plants and being the responsible for the Biogas Programme also including targets and measures for nutrient recycling.

At the moment, the continuing public funding for nutrient recycling include (as known at the time of writing) 1) Nutrient recycling subsidy for biogas plants digesting livestock manure and/or plant biomass from water restoration (Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry), 2) Ahti Programme, incl. RDI and investment subsidies for nutrient recycling, support for measures in the Archipelago Sea catchment (Ministry of the Environment), and 3) Investment support for farms (Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry) and large biogas plants (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment). There are also many other funding instruments for RDI projects, and the national CAP measures include subsidies for using organic biomasses and recycled nutrients on farms.

While the mindset of strong promotion of nutrient recycling in Finland has been rather steady for several years, the progress in practice has been slower. The barriers to quicker progress are often economic. The market for recycled fertilizing products is still small and with manure, direct use on fields has been the dominating method for use. The cost of processing nutrient-rich biomasses into more advanced and concentrated products has not been profitable enough as the willingness to pay for the products is often not high enough to cover the costs. Thus, most of the processing of nutrient-rich side streams contains rather basic solutions of anaerobic digestion, composting and mechanical separation. In larger processing plants this results in increased cost and complexity of logistics due to the need to find sufficient storage capacity and application sites for the products aimed at fertilization. On some processing plants, more

advanced products are produced, but the producer may get a better price from industrial use rather than from farms. E.g. some nitrogen-rich concentrates from biogas plants are sold to pulp and paper industry wastewater treatment.

Other barriers are related to potential risks of harmful compounds and practical arrangement of storing and applying recycled fertilising products. The concerns for harmful compounds are mostly related to sewage sludge containing fertilizing products even though in all studies conducted no risk of harmful effects on crops and their quality have been realized. Many significant buyers of the crops produced still decline purchase of crops which have been fertilized with recycled fertilizing products containing sewage sludge. In autumn 2024 the potential for impurities in recycled fertilizing products raised discussion as a news broke of visible, larger amounts of plastics in a digestate from a biogas plant digesting biowaste from grocery stores.

Farms may also decline the use of recycled fertilizing products due to the changes they require in farming practices. Suitable storage is needed, and not all farms have e.g. slurry tanks or solid manure storages usable also with many of the recycled fertilizing products available. The storages may also be available too far from the fields where the products are to be applied. Lack of application machinery or contracting services may also restrict the interest to use recycled fertilizing products. Most crop farms are accustomed to use mineral fertilizers applied simultaneously with seeding. Some farmers may also wish to avoid heavy application machinery on their fields due to soil compaction. Overall, the logistics and practices for using recycled fertilizing products need development in Finland.

2.1.2 Current practices

Finland has an indicator for monitoring the progress of nutrient recycling. Its first version was published in 2022 and is available in the statistical services of Natural Resources Institute Finland (<https://www.luke.fi/fi/tilastot/indikaattorit/ravinteiden-kierratyksen-indikaattori>). The aim is to update the indicator every three years so that a timeseries will eventually form. As the data on the biomasses, their processing and end uses are challenging to obtain as a solid flow from the site of origin to the end uses, it is expected that the indicator will also need development during the updating. In the following, the data follows the first results of the indicator (Luostarinen et al. 2023).

Livestock manure

Most of the manure produced in Finland (98%) is used as fertilizer in agriculture. Only approximately 7-8% of manure is processed, either in farm-scale or in larger facilities. Two thirds (2/3) of the share of processed manure are also used as fertilizing products in agriculture with the rest being directed mainly into horticulture and home gardening.

In 2023, around 410 000 tons of manure underwent anaerobic digestion. Most of this manure, 72%, is processed in smaller farm-scale plants (annual capacity 12 000 tons or smaller) which focus mainly on producing energy for the farm's own need (usually combined heat and power). Also, the nutrients are used on the same farm. Few farm-scale plants produce vehicle fuel (compresses biomethane) with their own delivery stations. In total, farm-scale digesters produced annually around 60 GWh of energy (data for 2023-2024). The highest share of manure in the farm-scale plants is dairy cattle slurry (84% of manure digested in farm-scale), while other manure types are rare. Most farms also co-digest manure with other feedstocks, such as excess grass or food industry by-products.

Recently, a newly revived interest in farm cooperative biogas plants and larger centralized biogas plants has been noted in Finland. The annual capacity of the farm cooperative plants is usually from 20 000 to 40 000 tons, and they often aim at producing vehicle fuel and reallocating the nutrients between the partner farms. At times, they may also sell part of the nutrients to neighboring farms (as such or after mechanical separation). On farm-scale digesters, digestate separation is rarer, and under 50% of the plants have invested in separation equipment.

There is one larger centralized biogas plant digesting mostly manure (total capacity 150 000 t) at the time of writing, but there are two other large-scale plants being built (with capacities 240 000 t and 420 000 t) and more being planned. Other existing Finnish centralized plants digesting small amounts of manure focus on processing other biodegradable feedstocks, and manure plays only a small role in the annual feed mix.

While the existing centralized manure-based biogas plant and one of the plants being built are investing in digestate separation and concentration of the liquid fraction, most of the other centralized plants plan to simply return the slurry-like digestate to the livestock farms providing manure to the plants. The challenge from the nutrient recycling perspective is then that little, if any, reallocation of nutrients is achieved, if manure nutrients simply “visit” the biogas plant and return to the same farms. It is also more than likely that there are more nutrients in digestates to be redistributed than in the feed manure as the centralized biogas plants often receive also other feed materials than manure to increase the biogas yield and to get gate fees. Additionally, there is no guarantee the livestock farms want to get the same amount of nutrients back than left the farm in manure. The plans to just return the nutrients to the livestock farms can thus become impossible in practice, and the centralized biogas plants will need to reallocate the nutrients also to crop farms and maybe also process the digestate to improve its sale, storability and transportability.

Of other processing technologies, composting is used especially for poultry (6% of poultry manure), horses (30% of horse manure) and fur animals (70% of fur animal manure). Some poultry manure is also dried and pelletized (6%).

Sewage sludge

The treatment of sewage sludge is rather strictly regulated to ensure its safe end use. The treatment, however, may not be the best for nutrient recycling, but more a reply to the need to dispose of the sludge in the easiest and least harmful way.

Most of the sewage sludge in Finland (76%) is anaerobically digested either in wastewater treatment plants or in centralized biogas plants focusing on waste treatment. Anaerobic digestion is applied as a sole processing method or in combination with composting the separated solid fraction of the digestate. Composting is also still directly used in processing of sewage sludge (17%), but its role is diminishing. Smaller amounts of sewage sludge are chemically treated or incinerated.

Approximately 40% of the sewage sludge is used as recycled fertilizing products in agriculture. Its agricultural use is restricted, not so much due to the requirements in the Fertilizing Product Act (711/2022) and Decree 964/2023 on Fertilizing Products, but due to the restrictions given by the food processing companies. Many of the large companies buying crops do not accept them if sewage sludge-based fertilizing products have been used. 46% of the sewage sludge produced is

therefore directed to other uses, such as landscaping. 14% of the original sewage sludge is returned to the wastewater treatment process during thickening and drying and thus recirculates in the wastewater treatment plants.

Of the nutrients in sewage sludge, it is estimated that 45% of phosphorus and 42% of nitrogen are recycled to agricultural use in Finland.

Municipal biowaste

The municipal biowaste is collected from households, catering services, restaurants and grocery stores in Finland. The source-sorting of municipal biowaste could be significantly improved as approximately 55% is still being incinerated or landfilled as part of mixed waste. Of the collected municipal biowaste 60% is anaerobically digested and 40% composted, with digestion becoming increasingly used. Thus, composting can be utilized as a post-processing method in the digestate treatment.

Of the original quantity of municipal biowaste, 54% is directed to agricultural use as fertilizing products while 23% is used e.g. in landscaping. 23% of the original mass is converted to gaseous compounds (carbon- and nitrogen-containing compounds) leaving the cycle. The agricultural use of recycled fertilizing products derived from municipal biowaste is partly restricted due to co-digestion with sewage sludge in some of the Finnish biogas plants.

Of the nutrients in municipal biowaste, 70% of phosphorus and 63% of nitrogen are estimated to be recycled to agricultural use in Finland.

Industrial side streams

Of the animal by-products (ABP) produced in Finland, 51%, mainly slaughtering wastes and animal carcasses, are directed to rendering and processed according to the demands of EU ABP regulation. Part of the ABPs can be processed otherwise, thus 7% of ABPs, for example by-products from fish farming, are digested, 2% composted and 40% treated with other means. Other means of processing cover different methods depending on the ABP type, where dilute wastewater fractions are directed to wastewater treatment and fatty streams are utilized in biofuel (biodiesel) production, while some ABPs are used either as feed for fur animals or incinerated.

Of other side streams from food processing, 42% of the quantity goes directly to field application, while 20% is digested, 2% composted and 36% treated with other methods, such as incineration or biofuel production.

Of all the side streams from food processing industry, 29% is used in agriculture as fertilizing products. 42% goes to other uses, such as feed or biofuel production, and 29% is lost as gaseous compounds depending on the processing method applied.

Only 29% of phosphorus and 19% of nitrogen in ABPs are recycled to agriculture as fertilizing products in Finland. The use of some by-products as livestock feed, however, provides another recycling route via manure. In addition, nitrogen and phosphorus in by-products directed to wastewater treatment and e.g. biodiesel production will likely end up in back in the circulation via municipal waste treatment either as part of sewage sludge or biowaste.

2.1.3 Policy instruments to promote nutrient recycling

Finland has implemented many policy instruments to promote nutrient recycling. Many of them are related to restricting overfertilization and reducing environmental impacts, but also to subsidize production and use of recycled fertilizing products.

The regulation of fertilization gives rules on what kind and how much fertilizing products are allowed to be used in Finland. But it also includes sections which are directly aimed at promoting nutrient recycling.

The purpose of Fertilizing Product Act (711/2022) is to ensure that all fertilizing products placed on the market in Finland are safe, of good quality and suitable for plant production. The Act also aims to promote the use of by-products suitable for use in fertilization, provided they have a proven positive effect on plant growth and do not cause damage or danger to humans, animals, plants or the environment.

Decree of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry on Fertilizing Products (964/2023) regulates the applicable raw materials, production processes and characteristics of the products for fertilizing products. The Decree and its Annexes give requirements and limit values for the product function categories and allowed component materials, similarly as in the EU Fertilizing Product Regulation. E.g. the limit value for impurities (glass, metal, plastic) is gradually becoming stricter, designed to give time for process development for recycled fertilizing products.

Government Decree on Limiting Certain Emissions from Agriculture (1250/2014, also known as 'Nitrates Decree', aims to reduce nitrogen emissions caused by storing and using manure and other organic fertilizing products and using inorganic fertilizing products. The Decree applies to the whole of Finland and all farms and implements the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC). E.g. in the minimum requirement for manure storages on farms, the use of farm-scale or other processing can be considered, if the processing reduces the volume to be stored.

Government Decree on Use of Phosphorus Containing Fertilizing Products and Manure (64/2023), so-called 'Phosphorus Decree' is the first stricter regulation for phosphorus fertilization in Finland. The aim is to reduce phosphorus loads to water bodies and to reduce the highest phosphorus concentrations in fields, while at the same time safeguarding the phosphorus needs of crops. The Decree regulates the use of phosphorus fertilization in agriculture, horticulture, green areas, and landscaping. It includes maximum allowable phosphorus fertilization amounts depending on the soil and crop in agriculture for all phosphorus fertilizers, including manure. In section 5 of the Decree, phosphorus recycling is directly promoted with allowing a small dose of phosphorus on field parcels with high phosphorus content, when the manure- or digestate-based product applied is recovered during phosphorus recovery into a separate fraction.

Finland offers also different subsidies in support of nutrient recycling. The most novel policy instruments offer impact-based funding. Operational grants for nutrient cycles are available for promoting nutrient recycling through biogas production in 2024-2026. The grants are awarded via competitive tendering to biogas plants digesting manure and the amount of funding received is tied to the amount of manure phosphorus digested in the plant and delivered to the use of other farms than producing the manure digested. During the tendering, priority is given to biogas plants located in regions of dense livestock production and/or surface waters with maximum adequate ecological state, and to using advanced technologies (minimum TS 25%, but additional

points given to TS >80%). The first tendering resulted in five biogas plants receiving the grant. A new round of tendering is being planned and negotiations to open a similar grant for other manure processing technologies are ongoing.

Another impact-based funding related to nutrient recycling is being piloted in the Archipelago Sea catchment of Southwest Finland during the coming ten years. The aim is to get farms to join the pilot, offering a grant for reducing high phosphorus contents in field plots. The funding does not regulate how the reduction should be achieved, but the methods are left for farmers to decide. The grant is paid if the phosphorus content in the field parcels chosen decreases. The soil samples are taken by the environmental authority to monitor the change.

RDI-funding has been available since 2012 from the ministries of Agriculture and Forestry and of the Environment. The same instruments have also granted investment support for full-scale implementation of measures improving nutrient recycling in existing processing plants. For now, these funding instruments are available until 2027.

The national CAP plan includes a measure to promote circular economy. It offers support for farms to apply manure and recycled fertilizing products via compensating the application costs. The aim is to ensure increased use of emission-reducing application methods (injection for slurry and digestate) and addition of organic matter into field soils.

2.1.4 Challenges in nutrient recycling

Despite a lot of work being done to promote nutrient recycling in Finland, the actual implementation is not progressing as well as is hoped for. The main reason is the economy of the nutrient recycling activities.

The production of high quality recycled fertilizing products requires significant investments which increases the true price of the products. Therefore, not that much advanced processing to concentrated fertilizing products is done. Furthermore, the farms are not sufficiently interested in using the recycled products, excluding organic farms. In comparison to mineral fertilisers, the recycled products usually require different storage and application methods which are not readily available, especially on farms specializing in plant production. This also reduces the farms' readiness to pay for the recycled products. Contracting services to transport and apply the recycled products are being developed and already available, but the change in farming practices is major. In the current economic situation of agriculture, not many farms are ready to pay for the use of recycled fertilizing products.

In relation to promoting more advanced processing, rather little is required by the current environmental legislation. Despite identified regions of surplus of manure and existing significant nutrient loading to surface waters, the environmental permits of processing plants do not sufficiently require the facility to organize proper use for the recycled fertilizing products. Thus, many of the large biogas plants do not process the digestate into more concentrated products but often use merely mechanical separation. Overall, the need to transport dilute products over long distances is a known challenge for many current processing plants. The challenge with the subsequent risk for unwanted environmental harms may increase with the new large-scale manure-based biogas plants.

To relieve both the economic and the regulation challenge, the share of recycled fertilizing products should be increased in the fertiliser market with a longer-term support from the society.

The funding available for supporting investments into production and increased use of the products on farms is currently too short-term. This makes the future of nutrient recycling less clear and reduces the willingness to invest. The change required is of a systemic nature which requires many simultaneous policy instruments of which some are already in place, but others can still be developed further. At the same time, the message for the businesses should be unified: nutrient recycling should always be also sustainably solved when planning other uses of nutrient-rich biomasses e.g. in renewable energy production.

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2.2 Estonia

Tiina Köster, Raivo Vettik & Kalvi Tamm, METK

2.2.1 Background

In Estonia, the main part of the raw materials for recycled fertilizing products comes from animal husbandry. At the same time, there is also an increasing amount of digestate from various feed materials due to an interest to open new large biogas plants, and it is important to find ways to valorize the digestate as organic fertilizers. Potential resources for nutrient recycling are also replenished by increased separate collection of food waste. In contrast, the use of composted sewage sludge in fertilization is strictly regulated, but here too, solutions are being sought to redirect the nutrient-rich sludge back into circulation.

2.2.2 Current practices

Livestock manure

Ca 85.1% from manure is applied directly to the fields as an organic fertilizer. Most of the rest is digested in biogas plants (see more below; Värnik et al. 2023).

Slurry is also mechanically separated in some bigger farms. Separated liquid fraction is directly applied to the fields as organic fertilizer. Some part of separated solid fraction is hygienized by composting and used as a bedding material in cattle farms. Another part of solid fraction is applied directly to the fields as a fertilizer.

Some farmers use in-store acidification of slurry to increase its sulphur content but also to minimize ammonia losses.

Most of the slurry is applied directly to the fields without any processing. In Estonia, biggest share of slurry is applied by incorporation technique and the smallest share by broadcast spreading

(Table 1). The slurry spread by broadcast and trail-hose has potential to be acidified with the aim to minimize ammonia loss.

Table 1. Usage of spreading technologies to apply animal slurry to the agricultural land, in Estonia. The proportions are calculated from total amount of slurry applied by these technologies in Estonian farms.

Spreading technologies	Proportion, %
Broadcast spreading	2.33
Trail-hose spreading	17.22
Incorporation spreading	40.17
Strip-till spreading	6.19
Open-slot injection	23.29
Closed-slot injection	10.79

Biogas plants

The main feed material in Estonian agricultural biogas plants is cattle manure, with lesser amounts of pig and poultry manure (Värnik et al. 2023). A share of 14.9% of the total manure resource including different types of manures is used for biogas production.

A total of 384 359 tons of feed materials were used in biogas plants. Of this, different manures account for 73.9% (284 158 tons) and additional substrates (Table 2) for 26.1% (100 201 tons; Värnik et al. 2023). The largest proportion of additional feed materials in manure biogas plants was food industry waste, amounting to 61 279 tons (Table 1).

Table 2. The amount (t) and proportion of additional substrates used in manure biogas plants (Värnik et al. 2023).

Additional substrate	Amount, t	Proportion*	
		Average, %	Range, %
Silage residues and grass silage	20 730	5.7	2.15–9.30
Cereal sorting waste	2165	0.6	0.00–1.03
Residues from the food industry	61 279	16.8	0.07–35.45
Vegetable waste	8651	2.4	0.00–3.45
Fat	2073	0.6	0.00–1.51
Yeast	942	0.3	0.00–0.84
Wood processing residue	4362	1.2	0.00–3.93
Total	100 201	26.1	10.01–46.24

* From the total input of substrates

Sewage sludge is digested in separate biogas plants. Of all sewage sludge produced, 45% is used in biogas production today in Estonia (Mötte et al. 2024).

According to the certificates of origin issued by Elering AS for 2023, 210.6 GWh of bio-methane were produced in Estonia, of which 33.6 GWh were produced from sewage sludge, 61.7 GWh from livestock manure, 42.0 GWh from food industry residues, 69.9 GWh from biowaste and 3.3 GWh from other biomasses. Depending on the type of bioresource, 3–45% (on average 16%) has been realised for biogas production, but 37%, 45% and 13% have been realised from raw

materials such as food waste, sewage sludge and manure, respectively. The authors point out that the results for food and biowaste have been calculated based on the known yield of biogas raw materials and the amounts of bio-methane produced (Sepp et al. 2024).

A good and quite unique example of digesting biomass collected all over Estonia is the EKT Ecobio plant near Tallinn. The plant reached full capacity in 2024, processing 80 t input material daily, i.e. over 20 000 tons of kitchen and canteen waste annually, producing over 1.52 million m³ of biomethane and over 19 000 tons of liquid fertiliser (separated liquid fraction) for the fields situated nearby in Harjumaa county. The biomethane was used as a transport fuel in the gas buses of Tallinn City Transport (TLT) traveling 2.3 million kilometers with it. Most of feed material is collected around Tallinn, but some comes also from other parts of Estonia. The feed material is cleaned from plastic and hygienized. The separated solid fraction is planned to be processed and market as growth substrate for plants.

Tartu Biogas AS also produces a certified digestate from biogas production. The feed material amount is ca 120 000 t annually (36 500 t biowastes plus agricultural side streams, such as manure, silage, straw, whey from food industry). Annual digestate production is 120 000 t.

Composting plants

In Estonia, some sewage sludge is composted, but [the sludge-based composts are not certified for fertiliser use](#).

Six landfill/waste companies are certified producers of compost from biodegradable waste. [Information on the amount of compost produced](#) is available for three of them:

- Väätsa Prügila AS - 22 000 t/a (handling of biodegradable waste and producing compost)
- Tallinna Jäätmete Taaskasutuskeskus AS – 35 000 t/a compost
- Paikre OÜ - 10 000 t/a compost

2.2.3 Policy instruments to promote nutrient recycling

Subsidies

Estonian investment support for achieving environmental and climate policy objectives of agricultural enterprises for the period 2023–2027 include measures related to nutrient recycling (Riigi Teataja published explanatory letter of the regulation: RT I, 11.03.2025, 10).

Climate change mitigation and adaptation: energy saving (e.g. technologies for heat recovery from liquid manure or compost).

Improving water and air quality: purchasing slurry and digestate separation technologies.

Biodiversity and soil protection promote the replacement of mineral fertilizers with organic fertilizers via purchase of composting technologies. This includes composting sites with collection channels and a bio-treatment plant ensuring the protection of surface and groundwater, composting based on plants, manure, sewage sludge and vermicompost production, compost and hay mixers, crushers and screening machines, continuous loaders – on a conveyor basis, compost covering – cover spreaders and reels, aerators and irrigation equipment, measuring equipment for measuring temperature, humidity, CO₂.

Additionally, a pilot project to support some municipalities to buy biowaste bins and composters for households was conducted (Biojätmete liigiti kogumiseks toetuste andmise tingimused ja kord – Conditions and procedures for support for separate collection of bio-waste; RT I, 14.09.2023, 1).

Regulation

Composting of solid manure on the fields in stacks is regulated by the Estonian Water Act (2024) § 165. In the same Act, § 166 regulates manure composting in more detail:

1. For the purposes of this Act, composting of manure means aerobic decomposition of manure, during which organic substances are decomposed by the effect of micro- and macro-organisms. For the purposes of this Act, composting of manure does not mean composting by composting equipment.
2. Manure may be composted primarily in a manure storage facility or in a stack on an area under cultivation. The quantity of manure to be composted outside a manure storage facility of an enterprise shall not be taken into account as a part of the capacity of the manure storage facility.
3. Deep litter manure can be composted in a stack only if the solids content of the manure is at least 25 percent when setting up the stack. The solids content of manure to be composted shall be determined from manure produced by similar technology at the expense of the producer before starting to set up the stacks at least once in every two years from one sample by the methods of analysis of an accredited laboratory.
4. The Environmental Board shall be notified of the formation and location of a composting manure stack by submitting a notice via the information system at least 14 days before starting to set up a stack.
5. Composting in a stack on the field is permitted in a volume not exceeding the limits for nutrients that are permitted to be spread on the same field pursuant to subsections 1 and 8 of § 161 of this Act. The height of a composting manure stack at the time of setting up the stack may be two meters in maximum, and the form of the stack shall preclude accumulation of storm water on the stack.
6. The manure to be composted shall be spread from a stack onto the field not later than within 24 months after starting to set up a stack.
7. After removal of compost from a stack, vegetation shall be planted on the ground of the stack located on grassland not later than by the beginning of the next vegetation period. A new composting manure stack shall not be set up in the same spot for a period of five years after the spreading.
8. The data to be set out in the notice specified in subsection 4 of this section and the procedure for submission of the notice shall be established by a regulation of the minister in charge of the policy sector.

The processing and use of sewage sludge is regulated in the Estonian Water Act (2024), in § 172 giving rules for the use of sewage sludge in green area creation, recultivation and agriculture.

1. Only stabilized or stabilized and hygienized sewage sludge may be used in the creation of green areas, recultivation and agriculture in tending of short rotation coppice.
2. For the purposes of this Subchapter, sewage sludge means a mixture of water and solid substance separated from wastewater using physical, biological or chemical methods.
3. Only stabilized and hygienized sewage sludge may be used in agriculture, except in tending of short rotation coppice.
4. The sewage sludge used in the creation of green areas, recultivation and agriculture shall meet the quality standards established pursuant to subsection 5 of this section, as well as other requirements.
5. The quality standards and requirements for the use of sewage sludge in the creation of green areas, recultivation and agriculture shall be established by a regulation of the minister in charge of the policy sector.

The § 173 of the act gives rules for maintaining records of the use of sewage sludge:

1. Persons using sewage sludge shall keep a journal on the use of sewage sludge or enter the data in the field record.
2. The obligation to keep the journal and field record shall not extend to natural persons if they use sewage sludge for own use.
3. Sewage sludge handlers who are waste handlers within the meaning of the Waste Act, shall keep a journal on sewage sludge treatment and transfer of sewage sludge for use.
4. The sewage sludge users and handlers shall preserve the data on the use or handling of sewage sludge for five years.

Regulation “Reoveesettest toote valmistamise nõuded” – “Requirements for the manufacture of a product from sewage sludge” (RT I, 14.04.2023, 10) regulates the requirements on products produced from sewage sludge. In addition to other requirements, § 20 gives rules for the use of products made from sewage sludge:

The locations for using products made from sewage sludge are as follows:

1. On agricultural land used for producing agricultural products and growing short-rotation coppice;
2. In landscaping for establishing or improving high or low greenery in green areas and green zones;
3. In reclamation for preparing land disrupted by mineral extraction or otherwise damaged land for reuse, or for covering landfills.
4. On land where products made from sewage sludge have been used, it is prohibited to:
5. Grow vegetable or berry crops, as well as medicinal or aromatic herbs, for one year after application;

6. Graze animals or harvest animal feed for two months after application.

Regulation “Haljastuses, rekultiveerimisel ja põllumajanduses kasutatava reoveesette kvaliteedi piirväärtused ning kasutamise nõuded” – “Limit values and requirements for the quality and use of sewage sludge used in landscaping, reclamation and agriculture” (RT I, 06.06.2023, 6) regulates the limit values on quality of sewage sludge and requirements on use of sewage sludge.

The sewage sludge resource is an important consideration when building biogas plants, as it helps achieve the EU's greenhouse gas emission reduction and energy goals. At the same time, biogas production is available in major Estonian wastewater treatment plants.

Sewage sludge can be certified as fertilizer if filled are the requirements in regulation “Nõuded biolagunevatest jäätmetest biogaasi tootmisel tekkiva kääritusjäägi kohta” – “Requirements on digestate resulting on biogas production from biodegradable wastes” (RT I, 14.04.2023, 9).

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2.3 Latvia

Zanda Melnalksne & Iveta Grudovska, Farmers' Parliament (ZSA)

2.3.1 Current practices

Livestock manure

Manure management differs between farms in Latvia, mainly due to four reasons: animal species, farm size, technological level and farm location.

In the most cases, manure is not processed. It is stored and used on the farm fields according to environmental restrictions and legal requirements. Allowed and appropriate technologies are applied for manure spreading and incorporation in the soil. There are just few places in Latvia, where there is a surplus of manure nutrient (hot spots). They are located around large farms and biogas plants. The operators of the mentioned farms cooperate with local crop farmers, and therefore the nutrients are delivered to the fields of other farms, to avoid nutrients excess application.

Some manure is composted together with bulking agents/materials. Manure compost is generally used for farmland fertilization.

Manure is also digested alone or in co-digestion with other feed materials in biogas plants. There are around 40 biogas plants in Latvia.

Latvia's largest poultry farm has invested in sustainable manure management processes. SIA EGG ENERGY invested more than 10 million euros in a biogas plant and fertilizer production plant in 2015. The production is totally based on poultry manure. The installed electrical capacity of the biogas plant is 2 MW producing annually approximately 16 million kWh of electricity. The cogeneration plant produces also thermal energy equal to the amount of produced electricity. The poultry manure is supplied by [AS Balticovo](#), which is the largest producer of eggs and egg products in Northern Europe. The digestate is converted into valuable fertilizers, a liquid ammonium sulphate concentrate (6 000 m³/year) and a granulated solid fraction (10 000 t/year).

Sewage sludge

Currently, Latvian sewage sludge is composted together with bulking agent. Compost is applied to agriculture fields and with other end users being e.g. municipal green zones and landfills. Sludge from two wastewater treatment plants is processed in biogas plants.

The Sewage Sludge Management Plan for 2024-2027 has been approved in Latvia, planning to reorganize and improve sludge management. The plan envisions establishing a network of sludge processing centers to promote economically viable sludge treatment.

The implementation of the Sewage Sludge Management Plan for 2024-2027 will ensure that all sludge generated in municipal wastewater treatment processes throughout Latvia will be managed according to unified principles. In establishing the procedures for sewage sludge management in Latvia, the plan provides for a centralized organization based on public water management (water supply and sewerage) service providers, as sludge generation is an integral part of their service. The plan proposes collecting sewage sludge generated at municipal wastewater treatment plants throughout Latvia and transporting it to appropriate processing (dewatering and other treatment) to larger facilities in the districts. Since not all districts

generate enough sludge to make local processing infrastructure economically viable, further centralization of sludge management is planned by establishing sludge processing centers at 27 wastewater treatment facilities. From districts where processing centers will not be established due to low sludge volumes, sludge is planned to be transported to the nearest processing center in a neighboring district.

The plan stipulates that the processing method at each center will be chosen by its operator. Studies and calculations conducted during the plan's development concluded that the processing methods that fulfill current EU and Latvian legal requirements for sludge management at the lowest cost are composting or so-called cold fermentation, where sludge is stored for 12 months. Sludge processed in this way can be used as a soil improvement agent, thus ensuring the return of nutrients to circulation through natural processes. The plan recommends choosing the most economically advantageous methods for sludge processing to minimize the impact on water management service tariffs. At the same time, the approved plan allows municipalities or processing center operators to deviate from the specified centralization model and processing method if another choice is justified through technical and economic analysis. For example, it is possible to combine several recommended sludge processing centers into one or transfer sludge to biogas producers.

Biogas production

According to data of the Central Statistics Portal for 2023, there are two biogas plants for sewage sludge processing and 40 biogas plants for other feed materials.

Intensive development of biogas plants in Latvia started at 2009, when feed-in electricity tariffs became available for electricity produced in cogeneration of the biogas and investment support was available for construction of the biogas plants. Feed-in tariff has been the main support instrument, providing guaranteed purchase prices for electricity produced from biogas. The support period typically was 10-20 years. Another similar was Mandatory Procurement Component (OIK), which established preferential tariffs for electricity generated from renewable sources, including biogas. EU funding programmes have provided investment support for biogas projects, particularly in rural areas. However, all mentioned support systems are currently stopped.

In recent years (up to 2024), several trends have characterized Latvia's biogas sector:

- Policy Shift - Latvia has gradually moved away from the generous feed-in tariff system toward more market-based mechanisms.
- Diversification of Feedstock - While initially many plants relied heavily on energy crops (particularly maize), there has been a shift toward greater use of agricultural waste, manure, and municipal organic waste.
- Biomethane Production - Increasing interest in upgrading biogas to biomethane quality for injection into the natural gas grid or use as vehicle fuel, aligning with EU renewable energy directives.
- Integration with Waste Management - Greater emphasis on biogas plants as part of circular economy solutions, particularly for municipal waste and agricultural residues.
- Sustainability Focus - Stricter sustainability criteria for biogas production, emphasizing lifecycle greenhouse gas emissions and avoiding competition with food production.

For the most current and detailed information about Latvia's biogas sector development and support mechanisms consulting the Latvian Biogas Association, the Ministry of Economics, or the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Regional Development of Latvia is recommended.

2.3.2 Challenges in nutrient recycling

There are several challenges for nutrient recycling sector in Latvia. The challenges are related to data availability, regulation, economy of processing plants and perception of the importance of waste management.

Regulation with changes in support schemes creates economic uncertainty leading to postponed investments. This is clearly visible in the biogas sector with challenges in biomethane market development resulting in slow growth in biomethane production for grid injection and transport. Support mechanisms do not suffice for large investments and challenges with legislation and cooperation with grid operators further reduce investments. Technical and administrative barriers to grid connection in some regions cause problems for electricity, heat or gas sales. The challenges also slow down promotion of nutrient recycling with less digestate to be reused in fertilization. Also, public perception is not always favourable. There is some local opposition to new biogas plants and other industrial plants, due to concerns about odour and increased traffic. At the same time, there is competition for biomass resources between sectors, for large lots of homogenous biomasses.

In the catering and food industries, a common understanding is missing about sustainable waste management issues. Also, there is no common system for food waste collection in the country, the organization of which could initiate more environmentally responsible attitude to the food waste management and improve nutrient recycling. Overall, a closer cross sector integration with waste management, agriculture, and district heating systems would support development of new nutrient recycling initiatives in Latvia.

Moreover, to monitor the nutrient recycling potential and its implementation, a lot of data is needed. In Latvia, information on the amounts and types of organic waste materials (outside agriculture) is not clearly available.

2.4 Lithuania

Edmundas Akstinas, Green Circle LT

2.4.1 Background

In 2024, agricultural production in Lithuania was 3.8 billion euros and harvesting was done from 2.8 million hectares of agricultural land. Main agricultural products are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Harvest of agricultural products in Lithuania.

Harvest of agricultural crops, Wool shorn, Milk yield, Eggs collected, Animals and poultry sold for slaughter

			2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	
Harvest of agricultural crops tonnes ^{1,2,3}	Republic of Lithuania	Farms of all types	Grain crops	6,935,409	5,621,328	6,013,990	5,997,112	6,197,082
			Sugar beet (for industry)	948,475	856,468	728,064	1,041,213	951,200*
			Rape	967,043	904,394	896,029	814,978	863,257
			Vegetables (field and under glass)	225,699	246,196	266,763	223,353	-
			Orchards and berry plantations	72,042	56,058	74,317	54,842	-
			Potatoes	302,604	204,624	231,825	274,480	298,000*
Wool shorn 100 kg	Republic of Lithuania		2,887	2,654	2,898	2,847		
Milk yield tonnes	Republic of Lithuania		1,491,676	1,476,887	1,521,936	1,472,973		
Eggs collected million units	Republic of Lithuania		881.2	876.1	816.6	831.2		
Animals and poultry sold for slaughter thousand tonnes	Meat, total	Carcass weight	275.9	259.5	261.6	249.7		

In 2024, the livestock reared in Lithuania included 623 522 heads of cattle, 497 091 pigs, 10 655 316 heads of poultry and 141 860 heads of sheep and goats, reflecting the overall trend in the country (Table 4).

Table 4. Number of livestock in Lithuania in 2020.

		Republic of Lithuania			
		Cattle, total	Pigs	Sheep	Goats
Number of animals and poultry at the beginning of the year units	2024	623,522	497,091	127,876	13,984
	2023	641,924	517,421	135,636	14,994
	2022	628,705	573,840	136,909	14,690
	2021	629,505	580,389	140,568	14,746
	2020	634,582	550,835	152,137	15,149

Agricultural production is affected by soil types and characteristics. Research data show that soils in a large part of Lithuanian agricultural land are becoming acidified, and these processes are most intense in Western and Eastern Lithuania.

In 2000–2011, Western Lithuania had 36.3% of acidic soils ($\text{pH} \leq 5.5$) increasing the 46.6% by 2012–2019. In Eastern Lithuania, the development in the share of acidic soils was from 24.0% to 30.0%, respectively, and in Central Lithuania from 4.3% to 7.5%. Over the decade, the highest increase in acidic soils was observed in the districts of Šilalė (19.0%), Tauragė (18.5%), Prienai (15.0%), Kazlų Rūda (10.7%) and Šilutė (10.4%).

Currently, the highest increase in acidic soils (Figure 1) is in Šilutė district with 72.4%, Varėna district with 70.5%, Šilalė district with 63.6%, Pagėgiai district with 61.5%, Plungė district with 58.4%, Tauragė district with 57.9%, Rietavas district with 56.5% and Šalčininkai district with 52.5%. This shows that intensive soil acidification is taking place in the country, and acidic areas are not being limed sufficiently. In the future, it is difficult to ensure a steady increase in the yield of agricultural plants in such unlimed soils, and in some areas the yield may decrease.

Figure 3. Soil nitrogen status in Lithuania.

2.4.2 Current practices

Livestock manure

According to HELCOM Declaration signed by Lithuania in 2013, it is necessary to comply with national standards for the amounts of nutrients (N, P) in animal manure and slurry to ensure appropriate and environmentally friendly fertilization, not exceeding 170 kg of nitrogen or 25 kg of phosphorus per hectare.

In 2016 and in 2020, the most common method manure application was broadcast spreading, where manure is incorporated into the soil within up to 4 hours of spreading. In 2020, broadcast spreading was most used by farms with 5–10 ha of utilized agricultural land (in 2016, farms with 2–5 ha of utilized agricultural land). Very few farms used injection method, where manure or slurry is injected into grooves formed in the soil.

In 2020, the largest number of farms (34 600) stored manure in open piles or in an open designated area. This accounts for 60% of all farms using manure storage facilities.

According to the 2020 census, most farms (92%) keep dairy cows tied up in barns with manure or slurry disposal. Only a small part of farms (7%) keeps dairy cows loose in barns with manure or slurry disposal. Other types of premises with manure or slurry disposal account for less than 1% of dairy cattle housing.

According to the 2020 census data, most farms (79%) keep other cattle tied up in barns with manure or slurry disposal. A significantly smaller proportion of farms (16%) keeps other cattle

loose in barns with manure or slurry disposal. 6% of farms keep other cattle outdoors all the time. Places where other types of premises with manure or slurry disposal account for 4% of all places for keeping other cattle.

According to the 2020 census data, most farms (88%) keep breeding sows in premises with hard floors (without deep litter) or in premises where the entire surface is covered with deep litter. 16% of farms keep sows on floors covered entirely with slats or partially with slats.

In 2020, most farms (87%) kept other pigs in premises with a hard floor (without deep litter) or in premises where the entire surface is covered with deep. 11% of farms keep sows on floors covered entirely with slats or partially with slats.

Laying hens are kept in battery cages mainly by large poultry farms (1.281 million animal places or 33% of all animal places). The fewest (0,491 million animal places) keep laying hens outdoors or in other types of premises. The largest number of farms (16 300 farms, 1.511 million animal places) indicated that they keep hens on deep litter.

Sewage sludge from municipalities and industries

In Lithuania, landfilling of sewage sludge, regardless of its treatment method, was prohibited. New treatment and reuse/disposal methods are therefore needed. Lithuania has already started to apply good practices for reusing sewage sludge as part of circular economy. The country has consistently developed an infrastructure for managing the sludge. According to the 2019 Environmental Protection Agency report, sewage sludge was treated in 12 fermentation and drying facilities, nine composting sites and two drying facilities. In 2017, the largest share of the managed sludge – 48.3% – was used for fertilization and recultivation, 38.7% was composted, 7.4% was disposed of in landfills, 5.2% was disposed of in other ways, and only 0.3% was incinerated.

Sewage sludge is seen as a promising raw material for nutrient recycling in many areas of food processing industries (for example, meat and fish processing, fruit, vegetables, grains, edible oils, cocoa, coffee, tea and tobacco preparation and processing, canning, yeast and yeast extract production, molasses production and fermentation, milk, sugar). The Wastewater Management Regulation requires that sludge obtained during wastewater treatment, grease accumulated in traps and other wastewater treatment waste must be transferred to waste management companies and managed in accordance with the established priorities. Exceptions apply when the waste can be treated at the place of generation together with grease generated during wastewater treatment or structural material required for the wastewater sludge treatment process obtained from other economic entities, or when wastewater treatment plants are operated, and waste is managed by a drinking water supplier and a wastewater manager.

In the food processing industry, the amount and quality parameters of sludge will partly depend on the products produced, production volumes and technologies used. For example, in the meat and fish processing industry, water is used in large quantities, as it is important for ensuring hygiene requirements. The sludge accumulated in flotation tanks is high in fat, therefore the characteristics and risks of such waste will differ from waste from fruit and vegetable processing plants, which may affect the selection of good waste management practices.

Raw sewage sludge is unstable, and the organic and inorganic substances and living organisms contained in it increase the risks of hazards in its use. To solve this problem, biological, physical and chemical methods of stabilization of organic matter are applied, which reduce the negative impact of sludge on the environment and the risks associated with this waste. The possibilities of sludge reuse as part of nutrient recycling depend on the sludge quality. On the one hand, sludge is rich in nutrients, especially phosphorus and nitrogen. Sludge releases nitrogen slowly, so after stabilization it can be returned to the soil as a fertilizer and soil improver. On the other hand, this material can increase the amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Wastewater sludge from the food processing industry can contain heavy metals (nickel, copper, zinc, lead, etc.), pathogens, pharmaceuticals and other undesirable substances, which makes the use of such material in fertilizer production potentially dangerous for the environment and animal and human health. Even the release of excess nutrients into the environment can have a negative impact on water bodies and soil, which forces the search for alternative safe ways of using sludge. Therefore, quality control of the treated sewage sludge aimed at fertilization and preventive actions to reduce contaminants are critical aspects that will allow for the effective use of sludge.

Sewage sludge can be used to diversify Lithuania's renewable energy sources to reduce dependence on fossil fuels via incineration. It is important to emphasize that such use often allows for the subsequent extraction of valuable nutrients for fertilization, but in practice this does not always happen.

Dried sludge can be burned as fuel. In Lithuania, facilities for producing sewage sludge granules to be used as biofuel are already operating. Such processing reduces the amount of waste, improves the economy of transportation and storage, and solves the problem of undesirable odor. Dried, safe sludge granules are sometimes used as fertilizer, but more often as biofuel.

The specific heat of sewage sludge incineration is like that of wood ($\approx 20\text{--}22$ MJ/kg SM), but the energy balance is often zero, since fuel preparation and combustion require approximately the same amount of energy as is obtained during sludge incineration. However, organizing the incineration process itself is also important, since the conditions and duration of sludge pellet storage can increase their moisture level and, accordingly, require more energy consumption when burning the same amount of fuel. The technologies used, logistics and the use of excess heat also affect the profitability of this process.

Recently, the attention of the academic community has been attracted by "sludge-to-energy" systems that aim for a positive energy balance and try to combine three key aspects: sludge treatment, energy generation and resource recovery. In the process, not only the gases released during the process, but also ash and slag can be used (for example, to produce cement, concrete or fertilisers).

If sludge incineration is carried out in mono-incineration plants, where only sludge is incinerated, the resulting ash may contain about 2–6% phosphorus and used for fertilization.

When incinerating sludge as a fuel, the ash obtained can be returned to the circular economy, so the composition of the fuel is important. Recently, the practice of incinerating sludge with other materials, such as food processing industry products, municipal waste, etc., has become more common in the EU. Such ashes often have a lower phosphorus content, and the final product contains other substances that make it more difficult to extract phosphorus. However, there may be desirable exceptions, such as a combination of sewage sludge and meat and bone meal.

Sewage sludge is an excellent raw material from which nutrients and energy can be recovered. In Lithuania, sewage sludge is mainly used in agriculture, for compost production, and in recent years, increasing amounts have been incinerated. Although Lithuanian wastewater treatment plants do not apply new and modern methods of nutrient recovery, successful application of circular economy principles in their activities is observed in many of the analyzed areas. An estimated 1.000.000 tons of sewage sludge is generated yearly in Lithuania.

2.4.3 Policy instruments to promote nutrient recycling

The Lithuanian “Environmental Requirements for Manure and Slurry Management” allow the usage of manure for fertilization purposes. It includes quality requirements and limits on nitrogen and application timeframes. The State Plant Service has allowed the following application limits:

- Total application of nutrients:
 - N - 210 kg/ha
 - P₂O₅ – 90 kg/ha
 - K₂O – 240 kg/ha
- If there is a fertilization plan based on soil analysis:
 - N -250 kg/ha
 - P₂O₅ – 150 kg/ha
 - K₂O – 300 kg/ha
- If fertilization is based on only manure / slurry application:
 - N - 170 kg/ha

It is seen to promote more precise farming practices, when higher usage of manure and slurry are allowed in the fertilization cycle.

The "Requirements for the Use of Sewage Sludge for Fertilization" set the rules and guidelines for sewage sludge to be used in agriculture. Although it is a highly regulated process, it is one of the most popular methods of sewage sludge utilization in the country.

The National “Fertilizing Products Act” and “National Fertilizing Products Identification List” allow usage of livestock manure and poultry manure-based fertilizers, animal manure based anaerobic fermented biomasses (digestates), and animal by-products on the market. Requirements for such fertilizers are based on the EU Fertilizing Product Regulation (EC) 2019/1009 and (EC) 142/2011.

These policies drive investment directions in Lithuania. The most promising route is currently anaerobic digestion of manure. In this sector huge investments are in the process:

(i) “Future Farm” milk production complex by Agrokoncernas: Milk production at the “Farm of the Future” in Miežaičiai (Radviliškis district) will begin in the first quarter of 2026. Nine farms will house 10 000 cattle, of which 4 000 are dairy cows. The farm will produce 140 tons of milk daily. This is the first stage of a long-term strategy worth 85 million euros; four more such complexes will be built in Kuršėnai, Anykščiai, Naisiai, and Akmenė over a 10-year period. A total of 20 000 dairy cows will be milked there (another 4 000 in the modernized farms of the complex) and 950 tons of milk will be produced per day. The project is expected to be completed by a milk processing plant. The "Farm of the Future" owns 3 200 hectares of land, the farm complex covers 52 hectares. Each of the 9 farms will house about a thousand cattle. It is promised that the principles of the circular economy will be ensured here, and biogas power plants will operate.

(ii) Akola Group: Kaišiadorys poultry farm managed by Akola group will build a biomethane power plant, where it will process organic waste generated in food production activities. They plan to invest 19.4 million euros in the power plant which should start operating in the first quarter of 2026. Natural gas costs in poultry farming are very high, because birds need stable heat to grow, and farms are heated with gas. Biomethane could replace natural gas in many cases. The Kaišiadorys poultry farm and other agricultural companies managed by Akola group and/or in the vicinity will process their wastes in the biomethane plants. It is estimated that up to 120 000-140 000 tons of manure and other organic waste will be processed per year. Each year, this biopower plant will produce more than 285 000 tons of digestate. It is expected that the biopower plant will allow to reduce the amount of CO₂ emitted into the environment by about 29 thousand tons annually.

Such investments surely will drive the need for recycled fertilizer production technologies. Currently, the most promising technologies biogas digestate valorization are: (i) Recycling of separated and captured ammonia in the biogas system and (ii) Production of digestate based organo-mineral fertilizers. These technologies show the highest potential to be utilized at large-scale capacities.

Figure 4. Digestate-based organo-mineral fertilizer.

Management of sewage sludge is geared towards phosphorus recovery. While the initial investments are in early development, currently explored routes by sewage sludge suppliers are:

- (i) Sewage sludge incineration technologies with subsequent extraction of phosphorus and potassium from the sewage sludge ashes;
- (ii) Pyrolysis processes to obtain biochar with extraction of phosphorus by leaching;
- (iii) Struvite production technologies.

2.4.4 Challenges in nutrient recycling

All the technologies described previously have a more or less clear pathway to the market, with the exception of biochar from sewage sludge, which is to be allowed in FPR EC 2019/1009 in the near future. The biggest challenges for sewage sludge is market acceptance: even though the technologies for hygienization and preparation of product are advancing rapidly, it is projected that it will take years if not decades to prove to consumers the safety and attractiveness of such fertilizing products in the food chain. Therefore, lots of investments in testing trials and communication strategies need to be allocated. Biogas digestate has already been accepted in the market, with Latvian A/S Balticovo showing successful implementation of both ammonia capturing and digestate granulation products supplied to the Baltic market. The real challenge now is to ensure proper strategies of large-scale implementation of such technologies in Lithuania.

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2.5 Poland

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2.5.1 Background

Nutrient recycling plays a key role in Poland's transformation towards a circular economy, in line with the aims of the European Union. Emphasis is placed on the management of manure, sewage sludge and biodegradable waste, aiming not only to reduce environmental losses, but also to optimize the use of resources. Great emphasis is placed in Poland on the management of industrial waste, which results from the significant role of the industrial sector in the national economy. The aim of the actions taken is to transform waste, which has so far been a burden, into valuable raw materials, enabling their reuse in production processes (Andrzejewska-Górecka et al. 2019).

2.5.2 Current status

Livestock manure

In 2024, the Statistics Poland published a report titled "Means of production in agriculture in the 2022/23 farming year". The report includes, among other things, information on the use of manures, understood as products that provide plants with nutrients and improve soil fertility. The report includes data for different manure types.

Data on the use of manures in 2022/23 were developed based on the preliminary results of the Integrated Statistics on Agricultural Farms (R-SGR 2023) cyclical survey. The results indicate that manure is used by 416 000 farms in Poland. Its national use amounts to 45.019 million tons (Table 5).

Poultry manure is used in 41 000 Polish farms in the total amount of 671 000 tons. Separately collected urine (liquid manure) is used as a fertiliser in 51 400 farms in the total amount of 7.573 million m³ nationwide. Slurry is used on 54 100 farms in the amount of 17.409 million m³. Three voivodeships stand out in Poland in terms of the use of organic fertilisers: Mazowieckie, Podlaskie and Wielkopolskie. In these three voivodeships, the use of manures dominates, as explained by the high concentration of intensive animal production.

Table 5. CONSUMPTION OF MANURES IN THE FARMING YEAR 2022/2023 (Means of production in agriculture in the 2022/23 farming year, Statistics Poland, Warszawa 2024).

VOIVODSHIPS	Consumption of manures			
	Solid manure	Poultry manure	Urine	Slurry
	in thousand tonnes		in thousand m ³	
POLAND	45 019.3	671.0	7 573.2	17 409.2
Dolnośląskie	652.1	35.6	130.5	154.7
Kujawsko-pomorskie	3 241.0	46.9	535.2	1 121.9
Lubelskie	4 122.2	35.1	296.7	610.6
Lubuskie	549.3	14.6	31.0	122.6
łódzkie	3 812.8	49.9	450.5	1 232.6
Małopolskie	962.7	17.4	332.4	239.4
Mazowieckie	7 332.7	114.4	1 234.7	3 265.0
Opolskie	906.7	19.7	266.1	496.7
Podkarpackie	603.8	31.3	188.7	123.9
Podlaskie	7 225.4	41.8	1 688.9	4 453.9
Pomorskie	2 030.7	42.5	374.2	1 017.1
Śląskie	780.8	8.8	162.5	191.1
Świętokrzyskie	950.9	24.8	121.4	184.5
Warmińsko-mazurskie	3 005.8	35.5	602.4	1 482.8
Wielkopolskie	8 059.0	131.7	1 119.1	2 496.7
Zachodniopomorskie	783.4	20.8	38.9	215.7

Manures are also used in agricultural biogas plants as part of the feed materials for biogas production. According to data from the National Support Center for Agriculture, the entity managing agricultural biogas production in Poland, organic fertilizers accounted for about 18-19% of the feed input used in agricultural biogas plants in 2022/2023. In 2022, 930 000 m³ of slurry, 95 000 tons of solid manure and 48 000 tons of poultry manure were digested in biogas plants, while in 2023 the respective amounts were 1 033 000 m³, 119 000 tons and 61 000 tons, showing an increase in the amount of manure digested in biogas plants.

Municipal sewage sludge

Municipal sewage is wastewater originating mainly from households and other municipal activities and may be mixed with industrial wastewaters and/or rainwater. The collection and treatment of the sewage are carried out by municipalities as part of the municipal sewage treatment systems. In recent years, to improve water and sewage management in Poland, the sewage treatment infrastructure has been significantly developed. New wastewater treatment plants have been built, existing installations modernized, especially in terms of nutrient removal, sewage network expanded and outdated facilities decommissioned. The effect of these activities is an increase in the amount of sewage that is treated, also using advanced methods of removing nutrients.

The sewage treatment process generates sewage sludge, which is formed, among others, in the fermentation chambers (digesters) of the sewage treatment plant. The amount and composition of this sludge depend on the adopted treatment technology. Thanks to the high content of

organic substances and biogenic elements, this sludge can find practical applications - among others as a fertilizer, a source of nitrogen and phosphorus, a raw material for compost production, as well as a material for the reclamation of degraded areas.

The importance of proper sewage sludge management is particularly important in the context of circular economy, energy efficiency and protection of non-renewable mineral resources, particularly phosphorus. From 2000 to 2022, there was an increase in sewage sludge production in Polish municipal wastewater treatment plants by about 63%. At the same time, thermal processing technologies are increasingly applied, which currently allows for processing over five times more sludge than in 2010 and results in a reduction in the required storage space (Figure 5). In 2022, sewage sludge accounted for 57% of the total mass of sludge produced in a given year (580 700 tons of dry matter), of which 18% (105 200 tons of DM) was subjected to thermal processing and only about 1% (8 200 tons of DM) was stored in the areas of wastewater treatment plants (Statistics Poland 2023).

Figure 5. Dealing with sewage sludge from municipal wastewater treatment plants in 2022 (Resources, use, pollution and protection of waters, Chapter 3 Environment 2023, Statistics Poland, Warszawa 2023).

Municipal source-separated biowaste

In Poland, in 2022, in total 8.2 million tons of municipal waste collected was subject to recovery processes, constituting 61% of all municipal waste generated. Of this, 3.6 million tons (27%) were recycled, 2.7 million tons (20%) thermally processed with energy recovery, and 1.9 million tons (14%) sent to biological treatment, such as composting and anaerobic digestion.

Separate collection of bulky waste remains at the level of 10-15%, but in 2022 it approached the lower limit of this range and amounted to 12%. The largest share of selectively collected waste was biodegradable waste (36%) and other fractions (17%), including mixed packaging waste (11%), multi-material packaging, used electrical and electronic equipment, hazardous waste and textiles.

On average, in 2022, 142 kg of collected or separately collected waste was produced per capita, including 51 kg of biodegradable waste. This is an increase compared to the 49 kg in 2021 (Statistics Poland 2023).

Poland places increasing emphasis on the biological processing of municipal biowaste, including composting and anaerobic digestion. The latter allows not only for the recovery of valuable nutrients, but also to produce biogas as a source of renewable energy (Szczepański and Waszczytko-Miłkowska 2022).

Industrial waste streams

In 2022, 115.0 million tons of industrial waste (excluding municipal waste) were generated in Poland, mainly from the mining (53.3%), manufacturing (18.6%) and energy (11.6%) sectors. About 48% of the waste was recovered, 42% was disposed of by landfilling and 7% by other methods (Statistics Poland 2023).

In the field of food and animal waste management, Poland applies the principles of EU regulation for animal by-products (EC/1069/2009). Industrial biowaste is mainly processed in biogas plants. Other waste is sent to composting plants or directly used as organic fertilizers.

2.5.3 Regulation related to nutrient recycling

The most important act in Poland comprehensively relating to waste management is the Waste Act of 14 December 2012 (Journal of Laws 2013, item 21) and its implementing regulations. According to this Act, all waste has been categorized, and individual groups of waste have been given appropriate numerical codes. The Act regulates the methods of waste management, including the so-called recovery. Waste that potentially meets the conditions of agricultural management may be subject to R10 or R3 recovery.

R10 recovery is 'treatment on the ground surface that brings benefits to agriculture or improvement of the environment'. In practice this means direct use for fertilization or reclamation of degraded soils. This regulates what types of waste can be subject to recovery and under what conditions (types of soil, method of use). Such waste management must also be in accordance with the Act on Fertilisers and Fertilization (Journal of Laws 2007 No. 147 item 1033). The following waste may be subject to R10 recovery: waste containing calcium, sewage sludge, waste containing large amounts of organic matter, excluding sewage sludge, and mineral waste.

R3 recovery involves recycling or recovering organic substances that are not used as solvents. These can be both organic waste produced in food processing plants and waste generated by farms or restaurants. R3 recovery can take place via composting, gasification (partial combustion) or pyrolysis, i.e. burning waste in anaerobic conditions or with minimal use of oxygen. The R3 recovery process can also produce products used for fertilization or reclaim impoverished soils in post-industrial areas.

In addition to the R3 and R10 recovery methods, waste producers can introduce waste into circulation in two ways: by recognizing the waste as a fertilizer or soil improver or by recognizing the waste as a by-product.

In the first case, products must meet given quality requirements and not exceed the permitted amounts of contaminants (heavy metals and microbiological contaminants) to be introduced to the market. Detailed guidelines regarding such fertilizing products (mineral, organic, organo-

mineral fertilizers and soil improvers) are included in the implementing regulation to the Act on Fertilizers and Fertilization (Journal of Laws 2024, item 1261)

In the second case, for the waste to be recognized as a by-product, it must meet a number of requirements described in the Waste Act, such as that the substance is an integral part of the production process, and its further use is certain.

2.5.4 Challenges in nutrient recycling

Poland's main challenges in terms of nutrient recycling include issues with regulation, subsidies and increased knowhow and cooperation.

Polish regulation already supports nutrient recycling, especially in the context of manure and sewage sludge. Regulation on circular economy exists, but the implementation is a challenge due to meeting the set requirements and some discrepancies in the interpretation of regulation.

The costs of processing biomass are high, which affects the final cost of the recycled fertilizin products. Access to suitable biomass for processing is not constant in many cases, which causes difficulties in maintaining continuity of production.

There are financial support programmes available, such as EU funds and national subsidies for nutrient recycling technologies, but they are often insufficient or difficult to obtain, especially for smaller entities. There is also a lack of coherent economic mechanisms that would encourage companies to invest in recycling on a larger scale.

The technology sector related to recycling organic waste is developing in Poland, and universities and research institutes are conducting projects in this area. However, there is a need for broad cooperation between science and business and for access to modern technologies in smaller enterprises. The development of effective nutrient recovery technologies requires further research and funding.

The acceptance of recycled fertilizing products by end-users is currently low. Their prices are not competitive in relation to mineral fertilizers, especially considering the price-nutrient ratio.

Also, further action is needed to more efficiently separate and process municipal and industrial waste, as well as to improve the logistics of transport and distribution of recovered nutrients.

2.5.5 Summary

In Poland, there is a large potential and demand for technology-based installations for wastewater treatment, manure management and organic waste processing. The development of such technology would positively affect the efficiency of nutrient recycling in Poland. However, despite technological support, Poland will continue to face challenges related to gaps in the recycling chain, limited financial incentives and the need to better use modern waste treatment methods. Further actions should focus on optimizing recovery processes, increasing cooperation between the public and private sectors and introducing more effective support mechanisms to close the nutrient cycle and reduce their losses to the environment.

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2.6 Germany

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2.6.1 Policy instruments to promote nutrient recycling

Many programmes have been implemented in the past to promote and increase nutrient recycling and promote a circular economy in Germany.

More than ten years ago, Germany adopted the German Resource Efficiency Programme (ProgRes), which was followed by ProgRes II in 2016. Aim of the programme is to fulfil the German sustainable development goals, to make products and consumption more resource-efficient and expand circular economy. Within the programme, P-recovery has been identified as one important component to establish a resource-efficient circular economy. Accordingly, the Federal Government committed itself to continue to support the industrial-scale deployment and diffusion of new phosphorus recovery technologies (BMUB 2016). One target defined in the programme was to significantly increase in the recovery of economically usable P from secondary sources no later than ten years after the new Sewage Sludge Ordinance (AbKlärV) came into force in 2017.

The Federal Ministry for Education and Research (BMBF) launched the funding measure „Regional Phosphorus Recycling“ (RePhoR) to contribute to the implementation of the new Sewage Sludge Ordinance by providing innovative economic solutions for regional P-recycling (BMBF n.d.).

The Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity (BMLEH) implemented the programme „Sustainable renewable resources ("Nachhaltige Erneuerbare Ressourcen" (FPNR)), which focuses on funding research and development especially in the area of sustainable production and use of biomasses from agriculture, forestry and waste management (BMEL 2024).

With view to biogas production the BMLEH financially supports concepts to increase the share of manure in biogas plants and to minimize emissions from animal husbandry (FNR n.d.).

2.6.2 Current status

Livestock manure

It is assessed that approximately 150-190 million tons of manure is produced in Germany each year. In 2021, approximately 60 million tons was used as a co-substrate for biogas production, with the remaining amounts applied directly as an organic fertilizer on agricultural fields (FNR, n.d). The digestate from biogas plants is usually also used as an organic fertilizer. Both products, manure and digestates can also be pre-treated before their application on the agricultural field.

A promising treatment-technique is the separation process, which is quite cost-efficient. The process divides the slurry/digestate into a liquid and a solid fraction (6-25% of the raw material). Project results report of a 40-47% reduced DM in the liquid fraction in comparison to raw slurry (Meyer 2024). Usually, the liquid fraction remains on the farm, while the solid fraction can be more cost-efficiently transported over longer distances. The solid fraction contains relatively high amounts of phosphorus and carbon and can be used as an organic fertilizer e.g. in regions with a lower livestock density and typically lower nutrient levels in agricultural soils. Alternatively, the use as a substrate for biogas production is possible (Meyer 2024).

There are no numbers available to what extend manure is currently separated and used further.

Beet leaves

There are existing techniques to remove beet leaves from the field. However, they are too costly and can only be found on large scale farms (Vogt et al. 2008). Therefore, beet leaves often remain on the field and are incorporated directly into the agricultural soil for plant nutrition and for enhancing humus production. Furthermore, beet leaves can be used to a certain amount as fodder (directly or silage) and as a co-substrate in biogas-plants (Wirtschaftliche Vereinigung Zucker e.V. 2023). Numbers regarding the share of beet leaves which are currently used as a fertilizer, biogas substrate or fodder are not available for Germany.

Cereal straw

There are many possible fields of application for cereal straw in Germany. However, the major share is currently used in agriculture. Straw is used as an organic PK-fertilizer and humus source for agricultural soils being directly incorporated after harvest. In animal husbandry it is used as a bedding material or fodder. When used in animal husbandry, straw enters the soil as a nutrient source in (solid) manure (Pfeiffer et al. 2019).

As a renewable resource, straw is also used in the packaging industry and building materials industry. In addition, straw is currently used to produce renewable thermal energy or biomethane (Pfeiffer et al. 2019).

Pfeiffer et al. (2019) refer to Weiser et al. (2011) and the DBFZ (Deutsches Biomasseforschungszentrum) database (reference year 2015) and indicate that each year between 33 and 38 million tons (FM) of straw is produced in Germany. Considering the required amounts of straw for e.g. ensuring soil quality and bedding material, an estimated 5 -13 million tons could be used for other purposes.

Municipal sewage sludge

In Germany, sewage sludge can be treated with one or more of the following techniques, depending on its future use:

- Thickening
- Dewatering
- Drying
- Conditioning
- Hygienization

After the treatment, the main share of the sludge is currently thermally treated (either incinerated or gasified), while the remaining share is mostly used directly in agriculture. The importance of the direct agricultural use of sewage sludge, however, is declining gradually in Germany due to new fertilizer and waste laws.

In 2019, 17% of the German sewage sludge were used agriculturally. In 2022, the share declined to 14%, while 80% of the accumulated sludges was thermally treated (Sichler et al. 2021, Destatis 2024).

A massive change regarding phosphorus recycling from sewage sludge can be expected for the future since the amended sewage sludge regulation (AbfKlärV) stipulates that from 2029 on, phosphorus must be recovered from sewage sludge, if it is concentrated with more than 2%. Furthermore, direct agricultural utilization will be prohibited for large WWTPs with >100 000 population equivalents (pe) from 2029 onwards and >50 000 pe from 2032 onwards. Only phosphorus recovery will be mandatory, but many processes aiming at phosphorus recovery recover also other nutrients (Sichler et al. 2021).

According to the German Sewage Sludge Ordinance (Verordnung über die Verwertung von Klärschlamm, Klärschlammgemisch und Klärschlammkompost [Klärschlammverordnung – AbfKlärV], a technique must recover at least 80% of phosphorus in sewage sludge ash (SSA), and techniques applied to sewage sludge have to recover at least 50% of phosphorus contained in it or have to reduce the phosphorus in the sludge below 2%¹.

As an example, the following scenarios and potentials for reutilization of and phosphorus recovery from sewage sludge in Germany are presented:

- Possible options for phosphorus recovery included are direct application in agriculture, and recovery from sewage sludge ash and sludges. For the recovery from sludges and ashes the following options are possible Sichler et al. (2021; Figure 6).
 - Precipitation with biological hydrolysis is restricted to treatment plants with biological phosphorus elimination. An optimum reduction of 30% of phosphorus was assumed,
 - Precipitation with acidic extraction of the sludge could achieve high recovery rates (approx. 50%).

¹ According to the Ordinance, P-recovery starts after finished wastewater treatment. Therefore, methods to precipitate struvite are technically not processes aiming for P-recovery. However, they can lead to a reduction of phosphorus in a sludge below the threshold of 2% and therefore no further recovery is mandatory after the finished waste water treatment.

- Other processes, thermochemical or metallurgical treatment and carbonation have a recovery rate of 80 % of phosphorus, potassium, magnesium and calcium. It should be noted that those processes are not necessarily applied at the WWTP.

Figure 6. Different recovery and recycling approaches for sewage sludge and sewage sludge ashes in Germany (translated from German into English; Sichler et al. 2021).

Municipal source-separated biowaste, green waste and food wastes from canteens and kitchens

There are many fields of applications for biowastes, and the composition and properties of the biowaste determine their most reasonable use (Figure 7, UBA 2024):

Wet bio- and food wastes are suitable for anaerobic digestion and subsequent use of the digestate (e.g. as a fertilizer);

Plant material rich in lignin and cellulose are suitable for composting and production of ready-to-use composts;

Wood-containing parts can be either composted or used energetically, e.g. in biomass power plants.

Figure 7. Possible utilisation of municipal biowastes in Germany (translated from German into English; UBA 2024).

According to the Regulation on the reclamation of biowaste of agricultural, silvicultural or horticultural soils (Verordnung über die Verwertung von Bioabfällen auf Böden [BioAbfV] ()), biowaste (if not covered by an exemption) must be sanitized before its application or use for the production of mixtures (§ 3, (1)).

Sanitizing means a biotechnological treatment of biodegradable materials for sanitation purposes thanks to:

- Pasteurization in accordance with Annex 2 number 2.2.1,
- Aerobic sanitizing treatment in accordance with Annex 2 number 2.2.2 (thermophilic composting),
- Anaerobic sanitizing treatment in accordance with Annex 2 number 2.2.3 (thermophilic anaerobic digestion), or
- Any other form of sanitizing treatment in accordance with Annex 2 number 2.2.4.

Currently, approximately 50% of German biowastes from households are composted; accordingly, the energy potential of those biowastes is not used. Therefore, it is aimed in the future to increasingly use the biowastes for anaerobic digestion, using both their energetic and material potential. Especially wastes from households (bio bin) contain great potential for digestion. The digestates, in turn, can be used as a fertiliser (Figure 6). According to the Federal

Compost Quality Association (Bundesgütegemeinschaft Kompost BGK) almost all the digestates are currently used as a fertiliser.

57% of all biowaste composts are used on farms as fertilisers (Figure 8; UBA 2024). Substituting mineral fertilisers with digestates and compost is one possible field of application. According to their nutrient composition, biowaste composts are usually organic NPK-fertilisers, whereas green wastes are organic PK- or NPK-fertilisers, since the N-contents in their dry matter are often below the declaration value of 1% (DM). P- and K-contents are usually above 0.3% P₂O₅ and 0.5% K₂O. If these minimum values are not met, the composts are identified as soil improvers (Möller & Schultheiss 2014).

Figure 8. Different uses of composted biowastes in Germany in 2023 (translated from German into English; UBA 2024).

According to their nutrient composition, bio waste composts are usually organic NPK-fertilisers, whereas green wastes are organic PK- or NPK-fertilisers, since the N-contents in DM are often below the declaration value of 1% (DM). P- and K-contents are usually above 0.3% P₂O₅ and 0.5% K₂O. If these minimum-values are not met, the composts are identified as soil additive (Möller & Schultheiss 2014).

Animal-by products

The use of animal by-products depends on the product categories (BMEL 2022):

- Category 1 (highest risk material) must be (co-)incinerated and the ash can be disposed of as waste.
- Category 2 (intermediate risk material) can be composted or digested in biogas production. The end-products can be used to produce organic fertilisers or soil improvers. The same is true for material of category 3.

- Category 3 (low risk material), besides being used as fertilisers or soil improvers, can also be used to produce fodder for production animals, fur animals or domestic animals under strict conditions and limitations according to regulation (EC) No. 999/2001 und guidelines according to food law.

Table 6 shows the share of animal by products for the different categories are illustrated for 2023. An overview of the products made from the different animal by-products is in Table 7. The precise utilization of the different products made from animal by-products are in Table 8.

Table 6. Raw materials of animal by-products in Germany (Beer 2023).

Category	2023 (t)
1	683 288
2	199 958
1+2	883 246
Share of animal carcass	406 640
3	1 851 762
LM	117 492
Total	2 852 500

Table 7. Products made from animal by-products in Germany (Beer 2023).

Products	2023 (t)
Proteins C1	150 964
Proteins C2	42 834
Proteins C3 (vtP*)	412 714
Greave (food product)	9 713
<i>Total Proteins</i>	<i>616 225</i>
Animal fat C1	71 439
Animal fat C2	24 404
Animal fat C3	281 683
Lard/tallow	78 303
<i>Total Fats</i>	<i>458 349</i>

* vtP = verarbeitetes tierisches Protein (processed animal protein)

Table 8. Utilization of the products made from animal by-products in Germany (in t, Beer 2023).

Product	Food products	Fodder	Tech. Usage ¹⁾	Biodiesel	Therm. usage	Own utilisation ²⁾
Protein C1					150 964	
Protein C2			42 834			
Protein C3		345 661	66 863			
Food (Greave)	1 420	8 293				
Animal fat C1				71 439		
Animal fat C2				24 404		
Animal fat C3		39 199	96 065	135 434	3 618	
Food-fat	10 627	24 974	6 712	28 732		

1) Fertilizer (proteins) or oleochemistry (fats)

2) Incineration for energy production

Proteins of *category 1* are usually used in thermal processes, i.e. in cement plants and other energy-intensive plants as substitute for fuel. Proteins of *category 2* are used as fertilizers after pressure sterilization by specialized companies to reach a significantly higher added value than thermal usage. Processed animal proteins (vtP) of *category 3* are mainly used as fodder (allowed since 2021) in the field of aquaculture, fur animals, and farm animals. The economically most important market for proteins of C3 is pet food production. E.g. greave meal with food quality is nearly exclusively used as pet food. Fertilizer use is currently at the share of 16.2% of C3 proteins. Exporting processed animal proteins has gradually gained importance over the last years. Approximately half of all processed animal proteins of C3 were of exported origin in 2023.

In 2023, animal fats of categories 1 and 2 were only used as raw material to produce biodiesel. Fats of category 3 are used as fodder (14.3%), in oleochemistry (35%) and to produce biodiesel (49.4%). The highest share of food-fats (tallow, lard and poultry fat) is used for biodiesel production (40.4%), 15 % as food and 35.2% as feed stuff. 9.4% were used in oleochemistry. Fats of all categories are used for biodiesel production. The major share is transported into EU-neighbouring states for biodiesel-production (see also Table 9).

Table 9. Use of animal fats in biodiesel production in Germany (in t, Beer 2023).

Category	Amount (t)	Use outside of Germany (t)
1	71 439	40 329
2	24 404	16 637
3	135 434	133 638
Food	28 732	23 942

BSG (Brewer's spent grain)

In general, there are many possible applications for BSG. It can be used as a fertilizer or fodder as well as for energy production in biogas plants. De-watered BSG can also be utilized thermally (Möller & Schultheiss 2014). However, in Germany, BSG currently is almost completely used as fodder for cattle, sheep, goats and pigs (TLL 2015).

Whey

Whey contains high amounts of potassium, calcium, magnesium and other mineral nutrients and trace elements. The elemental composition of whey depends on the animal species and the production process.

The fields of application of whey are manifold. In agriculture, it is used as a protein-rich fodder for pig breeding, for plant nutrition (usually applied by sprinkling or by using techniques to apply liquid manure) or also as a fungicide or virucide for plant protection (Landwirtschaftskammer Nordrhein-Westfalen n.d.; Möller & Schultheiss 2014, LfL 2012). The transport of whey to other regions is, due to its high water content, regarded as uneconomic (Möller & Schultheiss 2014). Information on how much whey is recycled back to agriculture is not available.

Grape pomace

Grape pomace is currently used in multiple ways: in the field of agriculture as a fertiliser, as fodder or as a biostimulant. The recirculation of grape pomace on the vineyard it originated from is generally allowed. The pomace must be broadcasted, it must not accumulate in heaps. If the pomace is recirculated within 5 days onto the space of origin, it is regarded as a crop residue and not as fertiliser application with view to the DüV. Accordingly, this application does not need to be documented. When applying grape pomace onto other areas, the nutrient contents applied must be considered and documented. Applied on arable land or green land, rules for the application of solid manure or compost must be followed (LWK 2022).

Several fertilisers or plant enhancers are commercially produced from grape pomace. The variety of these products is reflected e.g. by the products offered by the company Biovin (Biovin 2018):

- Bio-soil activator and long-term fertiliser
- Bio-NPK-fertiliser 10-3-5
- Humulus TK42+, liquid (humic acid extract for plant fortification)
- Bio-NK-fertilizer 7-2
- Biofertilizer 9N
- Biofertiliser 6-2-2, liquid

Furthermore, the use of extracts from grape pomace as an “alternative fungicide” replacing the application of copper have been proven to be effective (Ökolandbau 2025). However, these extracts are currently not used on a large scale.

Numbers, to what extend grape pomace is used as fodder or for the fertilizer/biostimulant production are not available.

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2.7 Denmark

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2.7.1 Background

Denmark exhibits the highest livestock density within the Baltic Sea Region with 1.59 Livestock Units per hectare of agricultural land (European Commission 2023). Approximately 61% of Denmark's territory is under cultivation, which is more than the double the EU average (European Commission 2022). With a population density of 141 persons per square kilometer, Denmark is the second most populated country in the region after Germany (European Commission 2025). These factors contribute to high turnover rates of nitrogen and phosphorus relative to other BSR countries. However, Denmark maintains a strong commitment to environmental integrity, motivated by both public health and economic considerations. Nutrient recycling plays a pivotal role in mitigating pollution and greenhouse gas emissions and is an integral component of Denmark's Water Action Plans, which establish specific targets for reducing nutrient losses.

2.7.2 Current practices

According to available data, Denmark's nutrient demand for crop production is estimated at approximately 380 thousand tons (kt) of nitrogen and 53 kt of phosphorus (Foged 2024). Of this requirement, 216 kt nitrogen and 48 kt phosphorus are supplied through livestock manure, 4 kt and 1 kt, respectively, are recycled from wastewater in the form of sewage sludge, and 22 kt and 10 kt, respectively, are recycled from other wastes and side streams, including food and industrial waste. Mineral fertilizers contribute an additional 238 kt of nitrogen and 11 kt of phosphorus. This results in an estimated surplus of 100 kt of nitrogen and 17 kt of phosphorus, which are released into the environment. Additionally, about 22 kt of nitrogen and 5 kt of phosphorus in wastewater are not recycled; most nitrogen is converted to nitrogen gas (N₂), while phosphorus becomes an inert compound. Agriculture accounts for approximately 90% of the total nitrogen turnover and 78% of the phosphorus turnover.

Agriculture

The first Water Action Plan was decided already in 1985, the so-called NPO plan (N= nitrogen, P = phosphorus and O = oxygen). The plan focuses on measures in farming, and later plans have gradually tightened and widened these measures, and have been aligned with EU policies, including the Nitrates Directive (European Commission 1991) and the Water Framework Directive (European Commission 2000).

The entire territory of Denmark is designated as Nitrate Vulnerable Zone according to EU Nitrates Directive. Annual instructions are issued for preparation of fertilization plans, comprising the maximally allowed nitrogen and phosphorus fertilization rates for various crops, and a set of standard values for livestock manures (Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri 2022). All farms must submit nutrient accounts to document that the allowed quota for fertilization does not exceed the regulated maximum for the farm, given its livestock manure production and the cropping plan. Furthermore, a Danish feature is that livestock manures as well as other organic fertilizers and end and by-products of organic wastes processing that are used for fertilization are associated with a so-called field effect, which is the minimum requirement to accountability of the nitrogen content of the specific organic or bio-based fertilizer. The field effect depends on the type of organic fertilizer, and is typically around 75%, meaning that farmers are not accountable for typically 25% of the nitrogen in such fertilizers (Styrelsen for Grøn Arealomlægning og Vandmiljø 2025).

A flat rate phosphorus fertilization maximum was introduced in 2016. The limit is 30-35 kg P per ha, dependent on the type of livestock manure or other organic or bio-based fertilizer type (Styrelsen for Grøn Arealomlægning og Vandmiljø 2025). The phosphorus fertilization regulation is thus well above HELCOM's recommendation of 25 kg of phosphorus in livestock manure per ha (HELCOM 2021). The regulation has not caused any major change of fertilization practices in Denmark, and the consumption of mineral phosphorus fertilizers (Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri, Landbrugsstyrelsen, 2023) remains relatively constant, leaving Denmark among EU countries with the highest P balances per ha of utilized agricultural area.

Requirements to manure storage facilities were introduced already with the first Water Action Plan. Broadly, the requirements mean that livestock farms must have a nine-month storage capacity to enable that livestock manures can be field-spread in the period of peak plant growth, to ensure the highest possible plant uptake of the nutrients and avoid leaching. Detailed standards are developed for construction of manure storages to ensure they are watertight and of sufficient size in relation to the livestock production. A large part of the slurry tanks has a solid cover to dramatically reduce ammonia emissions. Storage capacity inside the livestock houses is not allowed, and slurry channels must have max depths of 0.6 meters (pig housing) and 1.2 meters (cattle housing). Manure stores are registered and undergo inspections for every 10 years to ensure they are still comprising with requirements.

Most livestock manures are field spread in the period starting from 1 February, provided the soils are not frozen, snow covered, water saturated or flooded, until midsummer, with few exceptions for spreading livestock manures until 15 November. Liquid livestock manures, such as slurry, shall be spread by using either band-laying systems or injection, which is required for around 25% of the areas. Requirements for injection can be replaced by band-laying of acidified slurry or

separation liquids. Broadcast spreading of liquid livestock manures has been banned since 2001 for the sake of human health and reduction of ammonia emissions.

Based on the abovementioned situation and practices, the nutrient surplus described consists of an estimated loss of 49 kt of nitrogen and 9 kt of phosphorus from manure application (Foged 2024), attributed to regulated inefficiencies in nutrient recycling from livestock manures. While Denmark serves as a strong example of high nutrient recycling in farming, there is still significant potential for further improvement. As a result, the farming sector is positioned to play a significant role in increasing nutrient recycling.

Industrial side streams

Denmark's relatively high livestock production is apart from livestock manures also giving high amounts of wastes and side streams in the form of fallen stock and slaughterhouse wastes of around 75 000 and 535 000 tons, respectively (Foged 2014). These waste types are among other used for production of meat and bone meal. This could earlier be used as a high-value feed component for livestock but is of veterinarian reasons now only allowed for use in petfood, causing a large share becoming available for production of fertilizer pellets, which are especially valued in certified organic farming.

Denmark's dairy industry is not yielding significant amounts of organic wastes, since all milk components are effectively processed into food for direct consumption products or functional food ingredients.

Likewise, nutrients in byproducts of fruit and vegetable processing are not seen as waste but overall used as ingredients in total mixed rations for dairy cows or wet feeding recipes for pigs.

Municipal wastes

It is allowed to use sewage sludge for fertilization in Denmark, provided its content of unwanted substances are under given limit values (Miljø- og Ligestillingsministeriet 2018). Annually, this practice applies to about 80 000 t of sewage sludge. However, the value of this practice in a nutrient recycling perspective is questionable as most of the nitrogen content of sewage sludge is organically bound and due to the dewatering limited to a share of the nitrogen content in raw wastewater. Thus, most nitrogen in wastewater is converted to gaseous molecular nitrogen via nitrification-denitrification, and the rest found in sludge is not readily available for plants.

The practice of nitrogen removal is questionable from an environmental, climate and economic perspective. It is not only a waste of valuable nitrogen but also costs energy to process. Moreover, a part of the nitrogen is during the processing lost as emissions of nitrous oxide N₂O, one of the most potent greenhouse gases. Similarly, the phosphorus content of sewage sludge has typically been chemically precipitated during the wastewater treatment, causing a substantial reduction in the availability of the phosphorus for the plants. Furthermore, the sewage sludge is typically spread on the fields according to crop needs for nitrogen, causing overfertilization with phosphorus. Surprisingly, there is no nutrient accounting or nutrient recycling requirement to wastewater treatment plants.

Since July 1, 2021, a legal requirement came into force that requires all households in Denmark to sort food waste separately. It also requires municipalities to establish collection schemes for this purpose. The scheme was first fully implemented in 2024, where it was still impossible to

obtain reliable and solid information about the amount of nutrients in this fraction. Also, the municipalities are not required to make accounts of the nutrients in food wastes and have no goal for the recycling them. However, there is no doubt that the separated food wastes from households contain substantial amounts of nutrients, having a high quality from the fertilization perspective. The practice is that the municipalities dispose the food wastes to private biogas plants, where it is co-digested with livestock manures under the abovementioned 25% co-digestion limit.

Anaerobic digestion

There are 173 biogas plants in Denmark, whereof 92 agricultural biogas plants (Biogas Danmark 2025). The sector shows two-digit annual expansion rates, and slightly more than 40% of all livestock manures are processed at a biogas plant in 2024 (Biogas Danmark 2025). The biogas plants are predominantly large-scale and organized regionally, collecting livestock manures from many farms, and serving as a regional redistribution center for nutrients. Based on estimates for the entire Danish livestock manure production (Foged 2024) and the information about the number of biogas plants, it is estimated that the Danish agricultural biogas plants annually digest 15-16 Mt of livestock manures.

Danish agricultural biogas plants play a very important role in nutrient recycling. Conditions for subsidization of the renewable energy production includes the criteria that a minimum of 75% of the influent biomass shall be livestock manures, whereas the rest of the feed materials can be other types of biomasses. An exception are energy crops that can alone constitute up to 4% of the entire feed per biogas plant, and the use of maize or maize silage is entirely prohibited from 2025/26 onwards. The Danish Sludge Ordinance (Miljø- og Ligestillingsministeriet 2018), covering waste from households, institutions and companies, including biologically treated waste, processed wastewater and sewage sludge, to the extent that the waste is intended to be used for agricultural purposes, says that up to 25% of these waste types, on a dry matter basis, can be used for co-digestion with livestock manures, provided they comply with limits for unwanted substances. Apart from processed wastewater and sewage sludge, which are not co-digested in agricultural biogas plants, it is a common practice to co-digest with other waste and biomass types, including straw. The handling and use of the resulting digestate is regulated as livestock manures. In this way, there is a high confidence to the quality of digestates from agricultural biogas plants, which serves as a legal route for recycling nutrients in wastes back to farming without complicated end-of-waste approval procedures.

Not all digestate goes back to the supplying livestock farms, but much is delivered to specialized crop farms within a transport distance of up to 100 km, using it as valuable and effective fertilizer.

2.7.3 Nutrient policies

In Danish policies, nutrients play a significant role. Political negotiations on achieving Denmark's target of a 70% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 (relative to 1990 levels) resulted in the "Agreement on a Green Denmark" in 2024. This agreement includes a climate tax on farming and is expected to have a considerable impact on Denmark's self-sufficiency with plant nutrients. The plan outlines a reduction of nitrogen losses by 13 780 tons and the conversion of approximately 15% of the country's cultivated land into unfertilized forests and other natural areas by 2030. Projections indicate that a self-sufficiency of 55% for nitrogen and 109% for

phosphorus fertilizers could be reached. Higher recycling and 100% self-sufficiency are also feasible political choices.

Achieving the EU's overarching policy goal of a circular economy for nutrients would offer significant benefits for our environment, climate, health, soils, biodiversity, nature, critical raw materials, and overall welfare. Denmark is close to this milestone for phosphorus, with regional re-distribution incentives being the key to reaching it. For nitrogen, three principal focus areas provide a feasible path forward.

Firstly, it is viable to shift crop demands from crop economic optimal nitrogen dosing to society optimal nitrogen dosing. This would entail approximately 15% lower nitrogen fertilizer doses, thereby reducing nitrogen demand by 57 kt. This approach was implemented in Denmark from 1999 to 2015 and largely did not affect crop productivity statistics.

Secondly, the unaccounted nitrogen share in livestock manures can be progressively reduced to half, utilizing existing manure handling technologies on a broader scale.

Thirdly, there is substantial potential in modifying crop rotations to include more nitrogen-fixing crops, adopting regenerative farming practices, and incorporating microorganisms that mimic the ability of nitrogen-fixing plants to absorb nitrogen directly from the atmosphere and mobilize phosphorus in soils.

Besides that, it is essential, but also fair and reasonable, that wastewater treatment plants and waste collection companies meet the same nutrient recycling standards as the farming sector.

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2.8 Sweden

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2.8.1 Background

Sweden has a long record of measures to reduce nutrient losses to combat eutrophication, but strategies explicitly targeting nutrient recycling (NR) have emerged only in recent years. Early policies focused on phosphorus removal in municipal wastewater treatment plants which became widely implemented, substantially reducing discharges to surface waters.

In the agricultural sector, Sweden regulates manure use through the Swedish Board of Agriculture’s ordinance on environmental considerations in agriculture with regard to plant nutrients (*Statens jordbruksverks föreskrifter om miljöhänsyn i jordbruket vad avser växtnäring*, originally SJVFS 2004:62, most recently amended by SJVFS 2019:25). These rules apply nationwide and are stricter than the requirements of the EU Nitrates Directive, which otherwise apply only in designated nitrate vulnerable zones. Under the Swedish framework, manure and other organic fertilisers may not supply more than 22 kg phosphorus per hectare per year, averaged over a five-year period, in addition to the general ceiling of 170 kg nitrogen per hectare from manure. Livestock density is also regulated relative to available spreading area, linking

animal numbers directly to manure phosphorus excretion. These measures made Sweden one of the earlier adopters of P-based manure controls in Europe.

The debate on sewage sludge use has also strongly influenced Sweden's nutrient recycling policy. After extensive investment in phosphorus removal at wastewater treatment plants, attention turned to the quality of the resulting sludge. Concerns about contaminants such as heavy metals, pharmaceuticals, and PFAS led to systematic upstream reduction programmes. These were implemented by municipal wastewater utilities under the national general regulations for public water and wastewater systems (*Allmänna bestämmelser för brukande av den allmänna vatten- och avloppsanläggningen*, ABVA), which empower municipalities to regulate and restrict what can be discharged into sewers. Supported by national guidance from Naturvårdsverket (Swedish EPA) and Svenskt Vatten (Swedish Water & Wastewater Association), municipal utilities worked with industries and households to phase out hazardous substances before they entered the sewer network. These programmes significantly lowered heavy metal concentrations in sludge (Malmqvist et al., 2006, Svenskt Vatten 2023). Building on this, the REVAQ certification scheme was launched in 2008 by Svenskt Vatten together with the food industry. REVAQ goes beyond legal requirements by emphasising upstream pollutant reduction, monitoring, and traceability, while aligning with the SPCR 120 certification system that sets quality standards for digestate and compost. Together, SPCR 120 and REVAQ provide a framework for assuring the quality and safety of recycled nutrient products, though public trust remains mixed and political discussions continue on whether stricter limits or bans on sludge application should be introduced.

Policy responsibilities are distributed across several authorities. The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (Naturvårdsverket) oversees waste, sludge, and environmental regulation; the Swedish Board of Agriculture (Jordbruksverket) manages CAP implementation, fertilisation rules, and nutrient balance requirements; and the Swedish Chemicals Agency (KEMI) regulates pollutants. Municipalities play a central role in wastewater treatment and food waste collection. This division of roles reflects strong environmental governance but also results in coordination challenges.

In recent years, Sweden has sought to strengthen nutrient recycling through new instruments. The National Circular Economy Strategy (2020, Regeringen Diarienumret M202001133) highlights nutrient recovery as a priority. From 2024, all municipalities must implement food biowaste collection, and national targets state that at least 75% of phosphorus in wastewater be recycled by 2030, either through sludge reuse or ash recovery (latest changes to the Waste Ordinance 2020:614). Biogas production has been promoted through investment grants and renewable energy schemes, though limited capacity for manure and biowaste treatment remains a bottleneck.

Despite past policy efforts and the current framework, significant challenges persist. While on a national level P use is in balance, regional nutrient imbalances within Sweden are pronounced: southern livestock-intensive regions (Småland, Halland, Västra Götaland) face surpluses, while crop production regions in Skåne and Mälardalen depend on imported mineral fertilisers (Akram et al. 2019; Metson et al. 2022). This mismatch reinforces the need for processing and redistributing nutrients across Sweden to better align supply with crop demand. Sweden also failed to meet its 2020 ammonia reduction target under the National Emissions Ceilings Directive (NECD), and no adopted plan is yet in place to secure compliance with the more ambitious 2030 commitments. This gap highlights both the urgency of tackling ammonia emissions and the

opportunity to strengthen nitrogen recycling, turning losses into a resource for agriculture. Regulatory uncertainty on sludge, combined with low farmer acceptance of some recycled products, further constrains market uptake.

Overall, Sweden combines early adoption of phosphorus-based regulations and decades of proactive environmental policy with unresolved systemic barriers. While ambition and governance capacity remain strong, implementation is constrained by infrastructure gaps, regional nutrient imbalances, and contested public perceptions. Addressing these challenges will be critical to realising Sweden's nutrient recycling potential.

2.8.2 Current Status

Sweden generates large flows of nutrient-rich biomasses from agriculture, municipalities, and industry that could contribute to nutrient recycling, but current utilisation remains uneven across sectors and regions. Manure is by far the dominant source of nitrogen and phosphorus, and the majority is already recycled to farmland through direct field application. However, there remains ample scope to improve the effectiveness of this recycling by improving application techniques, and processing manure nutrients so they can be redistributed from areas of surplus to areas of deficit. Sewage sludge has long been reused in agriculture, though public debate and regulatory uncertainty have slowed its role in nutrient recycling. Biowaste recycling is expanding, particularly with the 2024 mandate for separate collection, but treatment capacity for digestate and biogas remains limited. Industrial side streams, especially from the forestry and food industries, represent additional but underutilised nutrient sources. Overall, while Sweden has strong regulatory frameworks and ambitious targets, practical nutrient recycling still depends heavily on a few streams and technologies, with significant potential for scaling and diversification.

Livestock manure

Livestock manure is the largest source of recyclable nitrogen and phosphorus in Sweden, with over 80 510 tonnes of N and 17 440 tonnes of P, accounting for more than half of the total nutrients applied to farmland each year (SCB 2023). Nearly all manure is returned to agricultural land, mainly as slurry or solid manure, but recycling efficiency is limited by nutrient losses during storage and application. Most slurry is applied with band-spreading techniques, primarily trailing hoses (74%), while 20% is still broadcast, resulting in higher ammonia emissions. About 76% of slurry is spread in growing crops, optimising nutrient uptake. The remainder is spread on bare soil and incorporated either immediately (10%) or within four hours (10%), practices that substantially reduce ammonia losses and improve nitrogen utilisation. Despite these generally good handling practices, there is still a need to increase nutrient recycling through improved nutrient use efficiency, particularly to reduce ammonia emissions at the national level and limit overall nutrient losses from agriculture.

Despite regulations linking livestock density to phosphorus spreading capacity, significant regional imbalances in phosphorus persist. The core issue is the low nitrogen-to-phosphorus ratio in manure compared to crop needs, which results in phosphorus over-application when nitrogen is applied at agronomically optimal levels. Over time this has led to soil P accumulation and persistent surpluses in livestock-dense regions of southern Sweden, while crop-dominated regions in central and northern Sweden remain dependent on imported mineral fertilisers. Analyses of Swedish nutrient flows show that large portions of manure phosphorus in livestock

dense areas either accumulates in soils or are lost from farms (Linderholm et al. 2012; Lorick et al. 2021). At the field scale, phosphorus leaching risk increases with high soil P levels, particularly when manure is applied to already enriched soils (Svanbäck et al. 2013). At broader scales, high livestock density has been directly linked to persistent nitrogen and phosphorus surpluses, reflecting structural imbalances between animal and crop production (Svanbäck et al. 2019).

Addressing these imbalances requires processing manure into transportable fertiliser products that can move nutrients from surplus to deficit regions. Techniques such as separation, nutrient stripping, and concentration could help align supply with demand and reduce dependence on mineral fertilisers. By contrast, anaerobic digestion for biogas production, when applied to raw manure, does not resolve the redistribution problem since digestion does not significantly affect the N:P ratio and it is still costly to transport. However, biogas plants could serve as hubs for further manure processing, offering economies of scale for nutrient recovery while simultaneously delivering renewable energy. Recent comparative life cycle assessments highlight that different manure treatment pathways (e.g. anaerobic digestion, solid–liquid separation) have divergent outcomes for climate change and eutrophication, underscoring the need to weigh environmental trade-offs in policy and practice (Lima et al. 2025). Current strategies in Sweden are beginning to emphasise regional reallocation of surplus manure and the integration of manure-based bio-based fertilisers (BBFs) into conventional farming systems, though economic and logistical barriers remain.

Sewage sludge

Sweden produces about 200,000 tonnes of sewage sludge (dry matter) annually. Nutrient concentrations average roughly 47 g nitrogen and 29 g phosphorus per kg DM, which corresponds to about 9,400 tonnes of N and 5,800 tonnes of P each year (Naturvårdsverket 2024). Nearly all phosphorus in wastewater ends up in sludge, whereas only about 23% of nitrogen are retained, making sludge mainly a phosphorus recycling pathway (Olsson et al., 2020). The nutrient content could replace an estimated $\approx 42\%$ of Sweden's mineral P fertiliser demand, but only $\sim 5\%$ of nitrogen.

The share of sludge recycled to farmland has increased from about 35% in 2017 to nearly 60% in 2024, mostly from REVAQ-certified treatment plants that operate under strict upstream contaminant controls. The remainder is primarily incinerated, with smaller shares used in landscaping or landfilled. While Sweden's land-application rate is high compared to many Baltic Sea countries, acceptance remains contested: food industry actors and some farmers continue to resist sludge-based products, citing contaminant risks and consumer perception issues, even when certification and quality controls are in place (Ekane et al. 2021; Lima et al. 2024).

Long-term field experiments in Sweden indicate that sewage sludge use contributes little to phosphorus recycling in the strict sense. Börjesson & Kätterer (2018) found that after 30 years of repeated sludge applications, only around 2% of the residual phosphorus became soluble and available to crops, while most remained bound in soils. Nitrogen uptake efficiency was similarly low (3–8%). This suggests that agricultural use of sludge functions more as a disposal route than an effective nutrient recycling pathway. However, the same experiments demonstrated soil improver effects: increased soil carbon content, reduced bulk density, and, in some cases, higher crop yields. These soil conditioning benefits remain an important driver of sludge application in Swedish agriculture.

Future directions include phosphorus recovery from incineration ash, which is now moving from research to industrial scale. Easy Mining's Ash2Phos plant in Schkopau, Germany, is under construction and expected to begin operation in 2027, while a second facility is planned in Helsingborg, Sweden, with start-up around 2028–2029. These plants will process about 30,000 tonnes of sludge ash per year and recover high-purity phosphorus alongside by-products such as iron, aluminium, and silicate fractions.

In parallel, source-separating systems are being tested in Sweden, through currently at a limited scale in smaller pilot projects in Skellefteå, Helsingborg, and Göteborg. The most advanced case is the Sanitation360 solution on Gotland and in Uppsala, which captures urine at source and processes it into a solid, nitrogen-rich fertiliser. While still at limited scale, such systems can reduce nutrient loads entering wastewater treatment plants while providing transportable fertiliser products, thereby complementing sludge-based phosphorus recovery with a pathway for nitrogen recycling (Aliahmad et al. 2025).

A 2020 government inquiry (SOU 2020) proposed two regulatory pathways for sewage sludge: either a complete ban on land application, or continued use under stricter standards, both combined with a requirement for $\geq 60\%$ phosphorus recovery at large treatment plants within 12–15 years. In line with this, Sweden's circular economy strategy sets a target that at least 75% of phosphorus in wastewater should be recycled by 2030, a goal expected to accelerate investment in safe recovery technologies. The ongoing debate over sludge application, together with stricter quality standards and forthcoming recovery mandates, may significantly reshape Sweden's wastewater nutrient recycling landscape. While land application under strict contaminant limits remains permitted, future regulations could further restrict this practice, reinforcing the need for alternative nutrient recovery technologies such as ash-based phosphorus extraction and advanced treatment methods (Ekane et al. 2021, KEMI 2025).

Municipal biowaste

Sweden separately collects and treats about 465,000 tonnes of food and other municipal biowaste annually (Avfall Sverige 2023). This material represents a nutrient stock of roughly 8,500 tonnes of nitrogen and 1,500 tonnes of phosphorus, assuming typical concentrations of 18 g N/kg DM and 3 g P/kg DM in digestate and compost (EBA 2024). Almost all of the collected biowaste undergoes anaerobic digestion (AD) or composting, producing both biogas and nutrient-rich digestate/compost for use in agriculture.

Despite these recycling efforts, a substantial share of organic waste still does not enter separate collection. In 2023, about 59% of Sweden's total municipal waste was treated by energy recovery through incineration (Avfall Sverige 2023). Although this figure includes all waste types, it illustrates that unseparated biowaste is still routinely incinerated with residual fractions, particularly in municipalities with incomplete collection systems. This practice contributes to renewable energy generation but represents a loss of recyclable nutrients.

Sweden has strengthened its policy framework to address this gap. The Waste Ordinance (Avfallsförordning 2020:614) requires all municipalities to provide separate collection of food waste from 2024, while national targets call for a 20% reduction in per-capita food waste by 2025. These measures are intended to increase biowaste recovery and align national practice with EU circular economy goals.

However, challenges remain. Plastic packaging and other impurities often contaminate collected food waste, lowering the quality of compost and digestate and limiting their acceptance for agricultural use under strict standards. As with sewage sludge, farmer confidence is shaped by certification, traceability, and perceptions of safety, which continue to influence market uptake. Treatment capacity is high, with permits covering ~2.3 million tons for AD and ~1.5 million tons for composting annually (EEA, 2024), but it is unevenly distributed across the country, leaving gaps in rural and northern areas and raising collection and transport costs.

Overall, municipal biowaste represents a growing but underutilized nutrient source in Sweden. While most separately collected material is already recycled into digestate and compost, significant nutrient losses still occur through the incineration of unseparated organics. Improving collection coverage, reducing contamination, and strengthening farmer trust will be critical to realizing the full potential of municipal biowaste as part of Sweden's nutrient recycling strategy.

Industrial side streams

Quantifying industrial side streams in Sweden is difficult. By-products from slaughterhouses and the food processing sector are not systematically reported in national waste or nutrient statistics, and available information is scattered across sectoral studies. This makes it challenging to assess the full nutrient recycling potential of these streams, even though they represent a significant but underutilised resource.

A recent survey of the food processing sector reported 305,000 tonnes of industrial food waste in 2022, of which about 214,000 tonnes went to biogas production, 20,800 tonnes to incineration with energy recovery, and 8,000 tonnes to direct land application, with smaller fractions composted or classified under other uses (Hultén et al. 2023). In addition, the dairy sector generated about 180,500 tonnes of by-products, mainly whey, which are largely repurposed as animal feed rather than treated as waste. These figures highlight the diversity of industrial side streams and their varying pathways.

Slaughterhouses are another major source of organic residues, including blood, bones, and offal. Partial figures suggest about 13,000 tonnes of cattle by-products were used for non-food purposes in 2020 (Glimaker 2023), but the total national volumes of animal by-products (ABPs) remain uncertain. Under EU and Swedish ABP regulation, Category 1 and 2 materials (high- and moderate-risk) are generally prohibited from agricultural reuse and are typically incinerated or rendered, resulting in nutrient losses. Only Category 3 materials (lower risk) can be used in feed, fertilisers, or biogas plants under controlled pathways (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2021; European Commission, 2023). Meat and bone meal (MBM), which typically contains about 8% nitrogen and 5% phosphorus (Spångberg, 2011), is an example of a nutrient-rich-by-product, but in Sweden most MBM is incinerated due to regulatory restrictions on agricultural use (Fuller, 2024). Some Category 3 animal by-products, lower risk, are processed into pet food or feed ingredients, and under defined end points a fraction can enter fertilizer routes (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel 2021; European Commission 2023). Some companies, such as Gyllebo Gødning, have to instead import MBM from Denmark (e.g. from Daka in Ringsted), underscoring the regulatory and market constraints that limit domestic use (Cederberg et al. 2011).

In the broader food industry, residues such as brewery stillage, vegetable peels and processing wastewater follow multiple pathways. High quality streams are often repurposed for animal feed, while the rest are directed to anaerobic digestion or composting. Although AD capacity has

expanded, high processing costs, logistical challenges, and uneven infrastructure limit large-scale nutrient recovery from these streams (Sar et al. 2022).

Overall, industrial side streams in Sweden offer substantial nutrient recycling potential but remain underexploited. Strong regulatory constraints on animal by-products, combined with logistical and economic barriers in food processing, mean that only a fraction of these nutrients re-enter agricultural cycles. Future opportunities include developing safe pathways for phosphorus recovery from MBM ash, expanding biorefinery approaches such as protein extraction or insect conversion, and improving aggregation and logistics systems to enable smaller plants to pool by-products for shared treatment. Unlocking this potential would make industrial side streams a more significant complement to manure, sludge, and municipal biowaste in Sweden's nutrient recycling strategy.

2.8.3 Challenges in nutrient recycling

Sweden's Environmental Code (Miljöbalken, Government Offices of Sweden 2000) establishes the overarching legal framework for nutrient recycling, setting requirements for fertiliser application rates and nutrient management plans to prevent eutrophication. The updated Waste Ordinance (Regeringen 2020) mandates separate collection of food waste by municipalities starting January 2024, with targets to increase biogas production and reduce organic waste to landfills. Agricultural Environmental Support (Naturvårdsverket 2025) offers economic incentives for farmers implementing sustainable nutrient management practices, including precision fertilization and use of organic amendments. The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency has developed guidelines specifying application restrictions for sewage sludge, including soil pH requirements, crop limitations, and mandatory waiting periods before harvest, which directly relate to the regulatory constraints mentioned in the current sewage sludge utilization challenges (Ekane et al. 2021). Municipal waste management ordinances require source separation of organic waste, with some regions implementing differential pricing structures to incentivize participation in recycling programs (Avfall Sverige 2023).

Economic Instruments

Sweden has policy interest and legal frameworks supportive of nutrient reuse, but national economic incentives for nutrient recycling are limited (Dioba et al. 2025). Investment support mechanisms exist for biogas infrastructure development, while renewable energy certificate systems provide revenue streams for biogas production from organic waste. Sweden applies PAYT (Pay as you throw)-type municipal fees, typically by container volume/frequency, with some weight-based systems, and biowaste is commonly charged less (sometimes free) than residual waste, to incentivize source separation (European Environment Agency 2022). However, economic barriers persist, as high investment costs for advanced treatment technologies continue to compete unfavorably with conventional disposal methods, and limited market demand for recycled fertilizing products faces price competition from mineral fertilizers (Aarikka-Stenroos et al. 2023, Pettersson et al. 2023). The economic viability of nutrient recovery remains constrained by transportation costs for redistributing nutrients across Sweden's large geographic area, particularly for redistributing surplus manure from livestock-dense regions to nutrient-deficient areas (Metson et al. 2022). Sweden-based farmer evidence indicates that price parity or a clear discount vs. mineral fertilizers, together with recognized quality certification, markedly increases willingness to adopt recycled fertilizing products. This implies that operating support

aimed at lowering delivered cost and performance-based premiums tied to certified quality could be more effective than CAPEX-only grants in driving uptake (Lima et al. 2024).

Regulatory Uncertainties

Sweden's nutrient recycling sector faces significant regulatory uncertainties that hinder investment and development (Johansson et al. 2024). The ongoing regulatory debate on sewage sludge application, coupled with stricter quality standards and phosphorus recovery mandates, creates investment hesitation as stakeholders navigate potential policy changes (Ekman 2022). While current policy permits land application under strict contaminant limits with an increasing focus on safe phosphorus recovery and reduced heavy metal content, a complete ban has been considered, which may significantly impact Sweden's wastewater nutrient recycling landscape (Ekane et al. 2021). These regulatory uncertainties are compounded by policies that are still evolving and require further alignment with EU Circular Economy goals, particularly in organic waste processing where infrastructure gaps persist due to regulatory uncertainties surrounding the use of composted materials in agriculture (Avfall Sverige 2023). Additionally, strict Swedish and EU regulations on animal by-products create barriers for broader nutrient recovery applications, with most meat and bone meal being incinerated due to regulatory restrictions on agricultural use, while regulatory and logistical barriers continue to limit the utilization of industrial organic waste streams (Pinto et al. 2022, Halim et al. 2025)

Technical and Infrastructure Challenges

Sweden faces several technical and infrastructure constraints that limit the efficiency of nutrient recycling operations (Metson et al. 2022). A governmental inquiry suggested biogas production to be increased from about 2 TWh today to 7 TWh by 2030, requiring rapid expansion and installation of several new biogas plants across the country, indicating current limited capacity relative to ambitious targets. Recent developments show progress, as St1 Biokraft has opened its flagship biogas facility in Mönsterås with an annual production capacity of around 138 GWh of liquefied biogas, making it one of the largest biogas facilities in Sweden (Bioenergy Insight, 2025), though Sweden's consumption of biomethane doubles its production, explained by Swedish incentives being focused on the consumption side, whereas most Member states subsidize production or injection of biomethane. Seasonal storage requirements pose significant challenges for organic fertilizer utilization in Sweden's climate, as manure is spread on the fields in the autumn and spring, avoiding spreading in the summer on growing crops because manure nutrients will vaporize on warm days, wasting valuable resources, and the domestic growing season generally starts in June and ends in August or September (Grusson et al. 2021, Lang et al. 2025). The establishing of consistent certification standards for nutrient content, contaminant levels, and overall fertilizer quality and efficiency is crucial for developing a viable market for recycled fertilizing products (Cordeiro & Sindhøj 2024). Yet, quality control challenges in ensuring consistent nutrient content remain a strong barrier, as food retailers worry about possible risks from pharmaceuticals and quality assurance when considering recycled fertilizing products (Magaya et al. 2025). These technical constraints are compounded by concerns over trace organic contaminants and the need for rigorous testing protocols to ensure product safety and farmer acceptance. Recent pilots with source-separated systems suggest that upstream separation of excreta can reduce treatment complexity and improve phosphorus recovery efficiency, thereby offering complementary solutions to conventional WWTP-based recycling pathways (Aliahmad et al. 2025).

Market and Social Acceptance

Market adoption of recycled fertilizing products in Sweden faces distinctive barriers rooted in complex psychological, social, and practical considerations that constrain widespread implementation. Swedish farmer acceptance patterns show significant regional variations, as a survey conducted during autumn 2021 to investigate Swedish farmers' perspectives on organic fertilizers use found an openness, broad interest and demand for different types of products of different forms and origin, though this demand will almost always depend on the price of products in relation to the price of mineral fertilizers (Álvarez Salas et al. 2024). However, farmer reluctance stems from deeply rooted psychological factors, particularly regarding sewage sludge-derived fertilizers, where fear of contamination and feeling of disgust are major discouragements of the use of sludge as an agricultural input, partly explained by unknowns and unfamiliarity about risks of unwanted substances in sludge (Ekane et al. 2021). Transportation costs represent a significant barrier, as the cost of transporting excreta in Sweden was three times higher than the fertilizer value transported at 5 km resolution, making it not cost effective without valuing other potential benefits of increased recycling (Akram et al. 2019). Consumer concerns about food safety significantly impact market acceptance in Sweden, as evidenced by restrictions by the food industry notably the dairy industry against the use of REVAQ-certified sludge on the same land as for milk production, mainly due to fear of contamination, brand reputation, and fear of losing customers (Ekane et al. 2021). Knowledge gaps represent a critical barrier, as perceived risks become overwhelming when there is no control of the actual risks, with the complex mix of contaminants such as PFAS, microplastics, and other substances of concern making risk analysis difficult. Swedish stakeholders emphasize that while actors engaged in the practice amplify benefits of sludge as a resource and emphasize upstream measures including improved risk management systems, actors in charge of controlling toxins amplify actual and potential risks and would rather have a complete ban on the practice. The market dynamics reveal that farmers are not the major drivers of the practice, with entrepreneurs playing key roles in promoting, monitoring, and evaluating the practice through building trust and convincing farmers to engage (Manyise & Dentoni 2021). These findings highlight the need for comprehensive education programs, improved quality standards, and enhanced risk communication to address misconceptions and build confidence in recycled fertilizing products technologies within the Swedish agricultural context.

Key stated reasons for non-use among Swedish farmers are shown in Figure 9. Note the split between operational barriers (compaction, spreading cost, handling) and market/quality barriers (uncertain value, buyer acceptance).

Figure 9. Swedish farmers' reasons for not using organic fertilizers (ranked by number of responses): soil compaction, access/availability, uncertain fertilizer value, expensive to spread, buyer acceptance risk, handling difficulties, and high purchase price (Lima et al. 2024).

Systemic Issues

In Sweden, the advent of mineral fertilizers enabled a decoupling of livestock and crop production, producing specialized animal farms dependent on purchased feed and regional nutrient surpluses, while crop farms rely on imported fertilizers; these patterns have contributed to eutrophication and soil degradation, with marked regional differences in ley use and nutrient balances (Granstedt and Thomsson 2022). This specialization has created a systemic disconnect where in other regions (on the plains), cropping farms dependent on imported fertilizers are dominant, while specialized animal production farms create nutrient excess gathering in some regions, leading to increased eutrophication of waters and emissions of the greenhouse gas nitrous oxide. Regional nutrient imbalances in Sweden stem from the historical decoupling of livestock and crop production: specialized animal farms reliant on imported feed generate surpluses in some regions, while arable areas depend on imported mineral fertilizers, with documented impacts on eutrophication and marked regional differences in ley use (Callesen et al. 2022). Economic assessments that include Swedish case work find negative net present values for several nutrient-recovery options due to high investment costs, indicating that stronger policy signals would be needed for wider recoupling to become viable (Akram et al. 2019). The systemic nature of these imbalances is further complicated by Sweden's general trend of declining livestock production, where in many parts of Sweden, the climate means that the economic return on crop production is generally weak, while grass production can be good, making forage processing by livestock the most important branch of production to keep agriculture active. Lack of integrated planning between waste management and agricultural nutrient needs represents a fundamental systemic weakness, as current approaches fail to optimize nutrient flows across sectors (European Commission 2024). The challenge is exacerbated by waste management trends that focus primarily on waste incineration and energy recovery rather than material recycling, which inhibits the development of small-scale local recycling businesses and limits opportunities for nutrient recovery (Gutberlet et al. 2020). These systemic issues reflect broader

challenges in achieving circular agricultural systems where scenarios result in lower nitrogen surpluses compared to average Swedish agriculture and thereby are a lower risk for contributing to eutrophication of lakes and seas, but this works in practice on farms probably due to increased humus content in soils which results in increased capacity for nutrient and water retention. Addressing these systemic challenges requires coordinated policy interventions that can bridge regional gaps, improve value chain integration, and align waste management with agricultural nutrient planning at both local and national scales.

Conclusion

Sweden has the policy ambition needed to lead on nutrient recycling, but the current system is not able to deal with regional re-distribution of nutrients to balance nutrient balances. Manure already returns the largest share of N and P to farmland, yet efficiency losses, regional surpluses in livestock-dense areas, and the cost of moving nutrients to deficit regions limit its circularity. Sludge remains an important, primarily phosphorus, pathway, but social acceptance and regulatory uncertainty constrain scale, while long-term trials suggest its agronomic role is more soil-improver than true P recycling. Municipal biowaste collection is expanding, but contamination and uneven infrastructure keep a sizable fraction of organics in residual waste and incineration. Industrial side streams hold clear potential yet are under-quantified and under-used because of regulatory constraints and logistics.

Closing these gaps will require shifting from “more tonnes collected” to “more nutrients effectively recycled where they are needed.” Three priorities stand out:

1. Target regional balance, not just national totals. Incentivise processing routes that create transportable, crop-ready fertiliser products (e.g., separated fractions, ammonia salts, concentrated P products) so nutrients can move from surplus to deficit regions at market acceptable cost. Treat biogas plants and larger WWTPs as regional hubs for upgrading and redistribution, not only energy facilities.
2. De-risk markets with quality and traceability. Scale up certification (e.g., SPCR systems and REVAQ) and transparent product specs (nutrient content, contaminants, agronomic performance) so farmers, buyers, and food companies can compare recycled products against mineral benchmarks. Couple this with clear end-use rules for ABPs (Cat. 3) and fit-for-purpose guidance for digestate/compost use on different crops and soils.
3. Align incentives with outcomes. Redirect support from primarily CAPEX and energy credits to performance-based incentives that reward measured nutrient outcomes: ammonia reduction, N/P delivered to deficit areas, and mineral fertiliser substitution. Where feasible, pair operating support with logistics credits for inter-regional transfers to overcome the transport cost barrier.

On wastewater, Sweden is poised to move from debate to deployment. Ash-based P recovery is entering the market; urine-diverting solutions offer a complementary nitrogen pathway and upstream load reduction. The near-term task is to integrate these routes with existing land-application where safe and accepted, while planning for contingency if future rules restrict sludge spreading.

For municipal biowaste, the 2024 collection mandate is a step-change; the next one is quality. Reducing plastics and impurities at source, standardising pre-treatment, and expanding regional outlets for clean digestate/compost will determine whether this stream becomes a dependable fertiliser source rather than an energy-only input.

Industrial side streams are the least mature but offer high-value niches (MBM ash P recovery, protein extraction, insect conversion, targeted co-digestion). Sweden should close the data gap (regular reporting of ABP and food-industry residues) and pilot safe, scalable end-points that can pass food-chain scrutiny.

Finally, monitoring must track outcomes rather than inputs. Suggested indicators include: (i) nutrients in recycled products delivered to deficit regions (tonnes N/P/year), (ii) ammonia and N/P losses avoided per euro of support, (iii) certified product volumes meeting agreed contaminant thresholds, and (iv) farmer adoption and buyer acceptance rates in key value chains.

If Sweden focuses policy and funding on these levers—regional balancing, quality and traceability, outcome-based incentives, and integrated hubs—nutrient recycling can move from promising pilots to a reliable, scaled system that cuts losses, displaces mineral fertilisers, and strengthens resilience in Swedish agriculture.

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3 Draft national nutrient recycling strategy

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This section provides a practical template for Baltic Sea Region countries to develop or update national nutrient recycling strategies. It translates the HELCOM Baltic Sea Regional Nutrient Recycling Strategy (2021)² into country-level action and operationalizes relevant priorities under the EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region (EUSBSR) Action Plan³ - Policy Area Nutri, with a focus on moving nutrients from surplus areas and waste streams back into safe, market-ready recycled fertilizing products.

Purpose and audience. The template is intended for ministries, agencies, regional authorities, and sector organizations responsible for agriculture, environment, water, waste, and bioeconomy in the BSR countries. It supports coordinated policymaking, investment planning, and monitoring regarding nutrient recycling.

How to use the template. Each country should adapt the sections to its context, set shorter- and longer-term targets, and specify who does what, with which resources and indicators. The template is structured as follows:

- **3.1 Mapping the nutrient recycling potential** - build the national evidence base (flows, qualities, spatial distribution, current uses).
- **3.2 Setting targets** – define measurable outcomes for collection, recovery, safe use, and regional re-allocation.
- **3.3 Measures** - regulatory, economic, infrastructural, market, and communication tools to reach targets.
- **3.4 Monitoring** - indicators, data owners, and review cycles to track progress and enable course correction.
- **3.5 Implementation & responsibilities** - governance model and coordination mechanisms.
- **3.6 Financing** - investment needs and funding sources (public, EU, private).
- **3.7 Alignment** - show how national measures contribute to HELCOM/BSAP and the EUSBSR Action Plan (PA Nutri), alongside EU Green Deal/Farm to Fork and related directives.

Guiding principles. When planning and implementing nutrient recycling, safety and quality of the end-products are important to ensure. Performance-based incentives should be prioritized to solve regional nutrient hotspots by reallocating the surplus to deficit areas. The practical implementation should be technology neutral focusing on lifecycle benefits, and transparent data for monitoring and accountability should be ensured.

A national nutrient recycling strategy should contain at least the following sections:

² HELCOM. (2021). *Regional Baltic Sea nutrient recycling strategy*. Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission. <https://rb.gy/r26atd>

³ European Union. (2021). *EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region: Revised Action Plan*. <https://eusbsr.eu/about/action-plan/>

3.1 Mapping nutrient recycling potential

A credible national baseline is likely to start with a systematic map of nutrient-rich biomasses across agriculture, municipalities and industry, compiled by a designated organization with secure resources and standardized methods.

Building on the approach used in the CiNURGi A1.1 report on nutrient recycling potential⁴, where BSR countries inventory livestock manure, municipal biowaste and sewage sludge, and relevant industrial side streams, the dataset would, at minimum, record for each stream the annual quantities and nutrient contents (N, P) and spatial distribution within each country at administrative and/or hydrological scales to reveal surplus–deficit patterns and logistical needs. Also, current treatments and end-uses, as depicted in this report, are needed. Given that several BSR countries underscore uneven data availability and fragmented monitoring, designating a responsible organization and reporting clear data ownerships with regular updates of mapping results could improve comparability.

Methods to map nutrient recycling potential are highly dependent on data availability and most likely vary due to this. One approach is to draw on established material-flow and budgeting frameworks referenced in JRC’s Knowledge for INMAP (2023⁵) work. It includes country-level nitrogen and phosphorus flows with distance to targets, and measures effects into web maps and dashboards. Any method used should include combinations of national statistics and modelled estimates, with open documentation of data sourced and uncertainties. It is advisable to make use of any other relevant existing data collection methods and indicators e.g. regarding gaseous nitrogen emissions to inventory greenhouse gas and ammonia emissions.

In practice, a staged plan may be helpful: first, collect existing statistics and other official data collections (e.g. livestock numbers, production of waste streams) and harmonize nutrient factors to nationally relevant levels; second, fill data gaps where possible e.g. with targeted sampling/interviews for key streams and facilities; third, produce national maps showing where nutrients are generated, where they are currently reused, and where agronomic demand exists; and finally, maintain an annual “nutrient recycling balance” that tracks how much nitrogen and phosphorus are recovered and returned to agriculture, and how much moves from surplus regions to deficit ones.

3.2 Setting targets for nutrient recycling

Targets are likely to be most credible where they reflect each country’s starting point and are traceable to existing EU and regional frameworks. A pragmatic approach is to define near-term milestones (e.g. 2027, aligned with HELCOM BSAP implementation, or 2030 consistent with the Green Deal objective to reduce nutrient losses by 50% while maintaining soil fertility) with nationally relevant longer-term targets. The targets should be aligned with indicators that EU Member States already report or can compile with modest additions. The country-specific chapters in the CiNURGi A1.1 reports show that the BSR countries are in variable stages of

⁴ Luostarinen S. (ed.) 2025. Nutrient recycling potential in the Baltic Sea Region. Report under preparation.

⁵ Grizzetti, B., Vigiak, O., Aguilera, E., Aloe, A., Biganzoli, F. et al., *Knowledge for Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan (INMAP)*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/692320>

implementing nutrient recycling and often fragmented monitoring of its progress. Thus, targets that build on what is already measured stand a better chance of being implemented and reviewed regularly.

A compact national target pack could therefore include four layers. Firstly, the separate collection of different nutrient-rich wastes and side streams could be improved to facilitate better recycling in the future. Secondly, the treatment of these streams could be targeted to be enhanced with improved nutrient recovery into safe, high-quality recycled fertilizing products. Thirdly, targets to solve the regional surpluses and deficits of recyclable nutrients could be set, making use of the concentrated recycled fertilizing products and following up on where the products are used. And finally, monitoring the progress (see: chapter 3.4) to ensure successful environmental performance should be set as part of the already existing reporting, such as ammonia emissions, gross nutrient balances, and nitrate concentrations in groundwater.

3.3 Measures to promote nutrient recycling

Experience across the BSR suggests that effective nutrient recycling depends on a coordinated set of regulatory, economic and practical measures that address the full chain, from separate collection and pre-treatment to recovery, product quality, logistics, farm use and market uptake. In regulatory terms, clearer and more predictable rules for handling nutrient-rich biomasses and for placing recycled fertilizing products on the market appear helpful, including e.g. hygiene requirements, contaminant limits and labelling that allow fair comparison with mineral fertilizers. Where national practice is heterogeneous, clarification of permitting and by-product/end-of-waste routes could reduce administrative delays for compliant materials. This direction is consistent with the country chapters' observation that uneven rules and quality assurance can slow uptake of the recycled fertilizing products even when technical options exist.

Economic instruments may work best when they acknowledge the current cost gap and pay for verified outcomes. This varies depending on the biomass and the processing technology. Evidence compiled by the JRC (2023)⁴ indicates nitrogen recovery costs typically around 1–10 €/kg N, depending on feedstock strength and technology, and phosphorus recovery from raw sewage sludge often exceeding 10 €/kg P, while struvite or ash-based routes tend to be more favorable. These figures help explain why purely market-based diffusion has been uneven to date. When avoided external costs, particularly from ammonia emissions, are considered, several measures become cost-beneficial at the societal level, which could justify targeted public co-financing that is tied to performance (for example, € per kilogram of N or P recycled to agriculture, or per kilogram of NH₃ avoided).

On infrastructure and markets, often the most advanced recycled fertilizing products can be produced in large-scale facilities, such as regional “nutrient hubs” at biogas plants and wastewater treatment facilities. They can reach the benefit of scale to concentrate, standardize and certify products, pairing phosphorus recovery with nitrogen recovery where feasible. Given transport costs and product characteristics, bulky composts and digestates are often most suitable for local soil-health benefits, whereas more concentrated products are better candidates for transporting nutrient over longer distances and resolving regional hotspots. Public procurement for landscaping and green areas, together with transparent certification and

labelling, could help create early trusted demand. Advisory services and fertilization planning tools that integrate recycled products may also support farmer uptake.

This report has noted that progress depends on simultaneous action by policymakers, businesses, farms, research and citizens; bundling measures and sequencing them, from data and quality assurance to targeted investment support, and then towards outcome-based instruments, could therefore be a prudent approach.

3.4 Monitoring the progress

Monitoring the nutrient recycling on a national level should combine a country-owned evidence base with nationally relevant and EU-aligned indicators so that progress, gaps, and impacts can be seen and acted on.

Each country should designate a responsible organization to maintain a national nutrient recycling dataset covering flows, product qualities, spatial distribution and uses, with secure resources and methods that are periodically reviewed. This responds to the A1.1 finding that comparable monitoring of potential, uptake and outcomes is currently fragmented and needs a clear data owner, regular publication and method improvement.

Building on current national and regional knowledge for integrated nutrient management, the monitoring pack should draw from existing reporting cycles and dashboards. To make recycling visible rather than only losses, the dataset should also track nutrients recovered and returned to agriculture by stream and product, the share delivered from surplus regions to deficit ones, compliance with safety and quality specifications, and verified environmental effects, using web maps and dashboards to compare regions and enable course correction. Regular (annual or every few years) public summaries should present trends against national and international targets. Mid-term reviews are also recommended to adjust targets and measures. This aligns with the report's recommendation to use monitoring as an active steering tool rather than a passive inventory.

3.5 Implementation and responsibilities

Implementation of all nutrient recycling activities should name a lead public authority and establish a formal coordination mechanism that brings together agriculture, environment, water, waste and bioeconomy mandates, with clear links to regional cooperation under HELCOM/BSAP and EUSBSR Policy Area Nutri. The lead ministry should chair an inter-ministerial steering group with regulators and paying agencies, while regional authorities, municipalities and utilities implement local measures (e.g., biowaste collection, WWTP upgrades) and report to national level. Industry organizations and farm advisory bodies should co-design standards, logistics and market uptake; research institutes provide methods, technology assessment and certification support. This aligns with the A1.1 conclusion that effective recycling is a systemic change requiring simultaneous actions by policymakers (regulate and incentivize), businesses (invest in safer, concentrated products and services), farms (adapt storage and application), research (methods, certification) and citizens (acceptance), with monitored progress used to steer policy.

To make responsibilities operational, countries could designate a national “nutrient recycling observatory” (statistical authority or research institute) as data owner for the evidence base and annual scoreboard. This body should publish harmonized indicators, such as nutrients recovered and returned to agriculture and shares delivered from surplus regions to deficit ones, so targets can be adjusted and incentives made performance based.

Coordination should specify who leads each instrument and how decisions escalate: e.g. national programmes for CAP and environmental funding allocate resources; environmental and agricultural regulators update permitting and quality rules; cities and utilities procure upgrades; farm and waste operators implement; and the observatory verifies outcomes. Routine cycles and a public report/website should enable course correction within a set timetable (annual or every few years). This mirrors the call in this report to designate responsible organizations for monitoring, ensure resources, improve data availability and methods, and compare progress across BSR countries to accelerate learning and alignment with HELCOM/BSAP actions.

3.6 Financing

The financing pillar should quantify the investment needs across the multi-stage activities being part of nutrient recycling and provide financial support for the different stages from public and private sources. The CiNURGi A1.1 findings underscore that economic feasibility is the main bottleneck; therefore, instruments should blend grants with results-based payments or depreciation support aligned to technology cost ranges and societal benefits. Practically, the national nutrient recycling strategy should specify which measures are grant-worthy, which can use blended finance, how advisory and certification are funded to unlock farmer uptake, and how monitoring is resourced to verify outcomes and recalibrate incentives over time.

3.7 Alignment with EU and regional policies

The national strategy should demonstrate how it supports and aligns with relevant EU and regional policy frameworks, including:

- **HELCOM Regional Nutrient Recycling Strategy (2021)**⁶ with its six objectives.
- **HELCOM Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP) 2021 update**⁷, particularly the eutrophication segment.
- **EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region (EUSBSR)**⁸ **Policy Area Nutri**, which promotes nutrient recycling within a circular economy framework and provides the governance structure and funding coordination for regional cooperation.
- **EU Fertilizing Products Regulation (2019/1009)**⁹ which establishes harmonized rules for recycled nutrient fertilizers, including quality standards, contaminant limits, and labeling requirements.

⁶ HELCOM. (2021). *Regional Baltic Sea nutrient recycling strategy*. Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission. <https://rb.gv/r26qtd>

⁷ HELCOM. (2021). *Baltic Sea Action Plan 2021 update*. Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission. <https://helcom.fi/baltic-sea-action-plan/>

⁸ European Union. (2021). *EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region: Revised Action Plan*. <https://eusbsr.eu/about/action-plan/>

⁹ European Commission. (2019). Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 170. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019R1009>

- **EU Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC)**¹⁰ on protection of waters against agricultural nitrogen pollution.
- **EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy**^{11,12} targeting 50% reduction in nutrient losses by 2030.
- **Other relevant EU and national environmental directives** such as EU Water Framework Directive, EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive, EU Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive and EU National Emission Reduction Commitments Directive.

The strategy should specify how national measures contribute to achieving these EU and regional targets.

¹⁰ European Council. (1991). Council Directive 91/676/EEC of 12 December 1991 concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources. *Official Journal of the European Communities*, L 375. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31991L0676>

¹¹ European Commission. (2019). *The European Green Deal* (COM(2019) 640 final). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2019%3A640%3AFIN>

¹² European Commission. (2020). *A Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system* (COM(2020) 381 final). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0381>

4 Conclusions

There is a large reservoir of nutrient-rich wastes and side streams produced in the agricultural, industrial and municipal activities in the Baltic Sea Region (Luostarinen 2025, report under preparation). While it is partly used as fertilizing products already, the recovery and reuse are not optimized, and a high share is lost either as emissions or into other end-uses and disposal.

This report shows that there are significant differences in the current activities and the ambition to promote nutrient recycling between the Baltic Sea countries. While some countries have long developed source-sorting and separate collection of different wastes and side streams, others are just beginning. Also, the level of processing different recyclable biomasses varies, even though the same EU regulation apply to all and gives a joint basis for the requirements to collect and treat them. National regulation gives further variation into how nutrient-rich biomasses are handled and how they can be reused or disposed of.

All Baltic Sea countries struggle with economic feasibility of nutrient recycling. Even the countries, which have implemented several policy measures to support and promote nutrient recycling, have challenges with building a working market for recycled fertilizing products much due to economic issues. The processing of the biomasses into more advanced requires high investments causing the real price of the products become higher than the end-users, i.e. farmers are willing to pay. This is also related to the often-different characteristics of the recycled fertilizing products in comparison to their mineral counterparts. The storing and applying the products need to be reorganized, causing another threshold to use them on farms. As the willingness to pay for the products remains low, also the willingness to invest in more advanced processing and production of more concentrated and controlled fertilizing products remains low.

The actual implementation of effective nutrient recycling requires a systemic change. To make it happen, requires several simultaneous measures from everyone in the recycling system. The policy makers need to both regulate towards improved recycling and incentivize to assist the economic gap between increasing production and end-use. The businesses need to invest and improve their technologies producing safer, more concentrated fertilizing products with a sufficiently high-quality to compete with mineral fertilisers. Businesses building supporting logistics and other services (e.g. transportation, storage, application, fertilization planning) are also required to make the use of recycled fertilizing products easy for the farmers (or other end-users). Farms need to understand the benefits of using recycled fertilizing products and adjust their activities enabling their use as part of the overall fertilization done. Research needs to support all these activities with policy support, technology development, and certification of the recycled fertilizing products for their safety and feasibility from the perspective of both crop production and the environment. Also, the public perception of fertilizer use in agriculture and the willingness to pay for the food produced with sustainable practices is needed.

The Baltic Sea Region is partly already on its way towards improved nutrient recycling and partly waking up to the need to recycle nutrients. The change is required is significant and cooperation between the different actors in the recycling chains are needed both nationally and internationally.

Thus, monitoring the status of nutrient recycling in the whole Baltic Sea region and comparisons between the promotion achieved, including how it has been achieved, are in a key role to push

nutrient recycling forward. The basis of the monitoring is to know the nutrient recycling potential in each country (Luostarinen 2025) and then regular surveillance on how and to the which extent it is made use of.

The Baltic Sea Action Plan ([HELCOM 2021a](#)) and the Baltic Sea Regional Nutrient Recycling Strategy ([HELCOM 2021b](#)) include several actions which include the need to know both national and regional nutrient recycling potentials and the current status of nutrient recycling as a means to enhance the efforts to reach more advanced recycling status. To enable such monitoring in a controlled manner, it is necessary to:

- Designate responsible organization(s) to collect the data on nutrient recycling potential and its status.
- Ensure required resources for regular monitoring and publication of results.
- Improve data availability for the monitoring as part of other data collections already existing.
- Ensure possibility to improve the monitoring methods and data exchange in an internationally equal level.

As shown in this report of the nutrient recycling status and in its sister report on the nutrient recycling potential in the Baltic Sea region (Luostarinen 2025, report under preparation), a lot of work is still needed to improve the monitoring and thus use it as a basis to promote practical implementation of nutrient recycling.

Moreover, to promote nutrient recycling, a strategy for its implementation should be made on national level to guide the steps ahead. The national nutrient recycling strategy should include the following sections at minimum, as stated in the strategy template of this report:

- **Map the nutrient recycling potential** - build the national evidence base (flows, qualities, spatial distribution, current uses).
- **Set targets** – define measurable outcomes for collection, recovery, safe use, and regional re-allocation.
- **Activate measures** - regulatory, economic, infrastructural, market, and communication tools to reach targets.
- **Monitor** - indicators, data owners, and review cycles to track progress and enable course correction.
- **Plan implementation & place responsibilities** - governance model and coordination mechanisms.
- **Finance** - investment needs and funding sources (public, EU, private).
- **Align with international targets, commitments and programmes.**